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AND BUSINESS**

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Exploring Multimodal Large Language Models for Medical Image Captioning

Marina Samprovalaki

Supervisors: Prof. Ion Androutsopoulos

Department of Informatics
Athens University of Economics and Business

Assistant Prof. John Pavlopoulos

Department of Informatics
Athens University of Economics and Business

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Marina Samprovalaki

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Department of Informatics

Information Processing Laboratory, Natural Language Processing Group

Athens, Greece

Abstract

Image captioning involves using models that combine methods from Computer Vision (CV) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) to generate textual descriptions of images. In the biomedical field, this process is known as Diagnostic Captioning (DC), where models automatically generate diagnostic text from one or more medical images. DC not only describes the images, but also interprets them to provide a diagnosis, helping healthcare professionals gain an initial understanding of a patient's medical conditions. To achieve this, researchers have formulated DC models that can interpret images and generate descriptions based on specified instructions. This study aims to unlock new possibilities in the biomedical domain by harnessing the power of Multi-modal Large Language Models (MLLMs) through techniques like task-specific fine-tuning and few-shot learning. It also explores innovative methods to integrate alternative image captions with a language model (LM) that has fewer parameters.

Περίληψη

Η αυτόματη περιγραφή εικόνων ενσωματώνει προσεγγίσεις από την Υπολογιστική Όραση (Computer Vision, CV) και την Επεξεργασία Φυσικής Γλώσσας (Natural Language Processing, NLP) για να παρέχει αυτόματα μια σύντομη περιγραφή των βασικών χαρακτηριστικών μιας συγκεκριμένης εικόνας. Στον ιατρικό τομέα, αυτή η διαδικασία είναι γνωστή ως αυτόματη διαγνωστική περιγραφή εικόνας (Diagnostic Captioning, DC) και έχει ως στόχο όχι μόνο να περιγράψει την εικόνα, αλλά και να προσφέρει μια ιατρική διάγνωση γι' αυτήν. Αυτή η διαδικασία αποσκοπεί στο να βοηθήσει τους επαγγελματίες υγείας να έχουν μια αρχική εκτίμηση της κατάστασης του ασθενούς. Στο πλαίσιο αυτής της διπλωματικής εργασίας, αναπτύχθηκαν και παρουσιάζονται μεγάλα πολυτροπικά γλωσσικά μοντέλα που αναλύουν εικόνες και δημιουργούν περιγραφές με βάση τις οδηγίες του χρήστη. Επιπλέον, αναπτύχθηκαν τεχνικές όπου δίνονται ζευγάρια εικόνας και περιγραφής ως παραδείγματα, με σκοπό το μοντέλο να μιμηθεί την συμπεριφορά τους και να παράξει νέες περιγραφές για άλλες εικόνες. Τέλος, εξετάζεται πώς ένα μικρότερο γλωσσικό μοντέλο, όσον αφορά τις παραμέτρους που χρησιμοποιούνται κατά την εκπαίδευση, συνδυάζει εναλλακτικές περιγραφές της ίδιας εικόνας για να δημιουργήσει μια πιο βελτιωμένη.

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Introduction

Medical Imaging is a scientific field that aims to develop innovative methods for visualizing the internal structures and anatomy of the human body [Sue09]. The most common imaging modalities are X-Rays, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Ultrasound (US) and Computed Tomography (CT). These medical exams are crucial for physicians in diagnosing and understanding the health condition. However, as the number of patients grows, radiologists encounter escalating demands with constrained time. Their intensive workload requires them to spend substantial time analyzing each case [Yan+22], increasing the risk of clinical errors, particularly for less experienced radiologists. Given these developments and the rapid progress in Deep Learning (DL) systems, substantial research has focused on developing Diagnostic Captioning (DC) systems. DC remains a challenging research area that aims to contribute to the diagnostic process by generating preliminary reports for patients. It should be noted that these systems are not intended to replace medical professionals, but to help them work more efficiently and at a faster pace [Mos22]. Moreover, automatically generated captions can help less experienced clinicians not only reduce the likelihood of mistakes but also improve their efficiency in making diagnoses [Pav+22]. To produce diagnostic text, both Computer Vision (CV) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques are employed.

In the current era of Large Language Models (LLMs) [Bro+20; Zha+23d; Min+24] and Multi-modal LLMs (MLLMs) [Zha+23a; Wu+23; Gon+23], researchers are exploring the use of these systems in the biomedical field [CFS24; YLW23]. These models have recently gained significant attention due to their effectiveness in a wide variety of NLP tasks. Their ability to understand the task and generate text arises from being trained with billions of parameters on large datasets that include text, images, and more. Furthermore, these models have demonstrated State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) performance on various tasks using In-Context Learning (ICL) [Liu+22; Don+24]. This allows them to generate text following instructions and drawing from just a few examples, without requiring task-specific training [Zha+23c]. In addition, these models can generate text by drawing from a pool of candidates or by combining information from multiple sources.

This thesis explores how MLLMs can analyze the details of an image and generate a concise caption. It also explores techniques to enhance and refine these captions by retrieving information from neighboring images that share similarities with the examined image, such as the same medical modality or the same organ represented [Lew+20; Gao+24]. In Figure 1.1, the first scenario is depicted, where a radiology image is used as input to the

model, accompanied by a prompt that helps generate a preliminary caption. In Figure 1.2, the second scenario is presented, where the model receives the same radiology image along with the generated draft caption and pairs of similar images with their corresponding captions. By utilizing the instructions provided in the users' queries, the model can leverage this additional information to refine and improve the initial draft. Additionally, this thesis examines a method of MLLM Ensembling [Ver+24; JRL23], where a more efficient LM integrates captions produced by various MLLMs.

Fig. 1.1: The first approach involves the model taking a radiology image as input, along with a prompt, to generate a draft caption that may be refined further in the next Figure.

Fig. 1.2: The second approach involves the model taking a radiology image, an initial caption, and a prompt as input, along with pairs of image-caption neighbors that display the same modality and organ, to generate the final caption.

The 2024 ImageCLEFmedical campaign¹ includes two sub-tasks: Concept Detection and Caption Prediction. As part of this competition, the AUEB NLP Group participated in both, this thesis primarily focuses on the Caption Prediction sub-task [Ion+24; Rüc+24a]. The Concept Detection sub-task considers medical image tagging methods, while the Caption Prediction sub-task focuses on the development of diagnostic captioning systems. Building on the previous work of the AUEB NLP Group [KPA19; Kar+20; Cha+21; Cha+22; Kal+23; MF22], we achieved 2nd place in Concept Detection and 4th place in Caption Prediction among 9 and 11 research groups [Sam+24] respectively, with the author serving as one of the main contributors. The code implemented during this thesis is available on Github².

1.1 Thesis Structure

Chapter 2: Background & Related Work

Chapter 2 offers background material and summarizes existing research on generic and diagnostic image captioning, as well as the application of LLMs and MLLMs in the medical domain.

Chapter 3: Implemented Methods & Systems

Chapter 3 contains the methods and systems developed and implemented as part of this thesis.

Chapter 4: Data

Chapter 4 provides an overview of the dataset used for model development, including general information and an in-depth exploratory analysis.

Chapter 5: Experiments & Results

Chapter 5 introduces the evaluation metrics used and presents the experimental results for each implemented model.

Chapter 6: Conclusions & Future Work

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions drawn from the work of this thesis and potential directions for future work in the field of NLP.

¹<https://www.imageclef.org>, Last accessed: 2024-11-30

² Github Repository

Background and Related Work

This section offers insights and technical details on prior work in the fields of NLP, CV, and DL that have achieved SOTA performance in both generic and diagnostic captioning. Additionally, it explores the application of LLMs and MLLMs in the biomedical domain.

Generic image captioning [Als+19] involves generating textual descriptions, or captions, that describe the content of an image. This process typically involves either a generation or retrieval approach facilitated by a learning model. Figure 2.1 displays some examples of captions generated by the LLaVA-1,5 [Liu+24a] model.

(a) The image features a woman standing on a wet sidewalk, holding a red umbrella to protect herself from the rain. She is accompanied by a black dog, which is sitting on the ground next to her.

(b) The image captures a thrilling moment during a basketball game, where a player is leaping into the air to dunk the ball through the hoop.

(c) The image features a small, orange and white cat sitting on a wooden table. The cat appears to be looking sad or lonely, as it is sitting alone on the table.

Fig. 2.1: Examples of image captions generated by the LLaVA-1,5 model.

Image captioning techniques serve as a foundation for applications in domains such as DC. Unlike generic image captioning, which primarily describes the visual content of an image, DC focuses on generating captions that convey clinically relevant medical information. Examples of medical image and diagnostic caption pairs can be found in Figure 2.2.

2.1 Generic Image Captioning

In the field of Generic Image Captioning, a variety of approaches have been developed over the years. Some of the early experiments in this area were conducted by Farhadi et al. [Far+10], who linked images to sentences by calculating similarity scores between an image and a set of candidate captions. Image captioning is generally viewed as a process of transforming images into text sequences. Before the advent of neural NLP

(a) chest x-ray (cxr) showed diffuse patchy lung infiltrates, concerning possible venous congestion or pulmonary edema with enlargement of the cardio-mediastinal silhouette. CC BY Muacevic et al. (2021)

(b) abdominal computed tomography (ct) displaying a large cystic lesion (arrow) adjacent to the right liver lobe, the stomach, and the pancreatic head. CC BY De Vogelaere et al. (2012)

(c) brain nuclear magnetic resonance images of the axial planes using flair (tr 9002.2, te 152.2 ti 2200ms), on July 12, 2011 showing supra and infratentorial involvement. CC BY Champs et al. (2013)

Fig. 2.2: Diagnostic imaging examples taken from the ImageCLEF2024 dataset [Rüc+24a].

techniques, research in image captioning often relied on Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) [PR20; AMD21]. These models would predict the next word based on the current context by examining word sequences, their order, and how often they appeared in existing text. However, they struggled to fully grasp the meaning or context behind the generated word sequences.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [ON15] have been the dominant approach for image processing for many years, excelling at extracting meaningful features and representations from image data. Moreover, the introduction of models such as the Vision Transformer (ViT) [Dos+21] represents a significant step forward in image recognition. ViT is notable for applying the Transformer architecture [Vas+17] to visual tasks. Unlike traditional CNNs that process images through layers of convolutions, ViT treats images as sequences of patches, akin to how words are treated in text. Each image is divided into fixed-size patches that are then converted into vectors through linear embeddings. These vectors are processed by the attention mechanisms used in Transformers [Vas+17], which effectively capture global context and relationships across the entire image. By pre-training on extensive image datasets with a classification objective, ViT learns to extract rich, high-level features and has achieved SOTA performance in various image-related tasks [Dos+21]. Figure 2.3 provides an overview of the ViT architecture [Dos+21]. Initially, the image is divided into fixed-size patches. Positional embeddings are then added to these patches to provide the model with information about the position of each patch in the sequence. The resulting sequence of embedded patches is fed into a standard Transformer encoder.

As for text generation, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [Sch19] were very popular a few years ago. Using special RNN cells such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [HS97] and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) [Chu+14] led to significant performance improvements

Fig. 2.3: The ViT architecture where the image is partitioned into patches, which are subsequently flattened and projected into embeddings. These embeddings are then input into a multi-layer transformer encoder. Finally, the output associated with the class token is passed through an MLP head to perform image classification. Figure taken from [Dos+21].

compared to vanilla RNNs, also making them faster and more effective. This was a significant step forward because RNNs could process input sequences one word at a time, helping to predict the next word in the sentence. Despite these advancements, RNNs, including GRU and LSTM models, had their own challenges, particularly when it came to capturing long-range dependencies in text. As input sequences grew longer, these models faced bottlenecks that made it difficult to retain all the necessary information and context. This was especially challenging because they were unable to process the sequences in parallel [She20]. The introduction of attention mechanisms marked a real turning point. This led to the creation of Transformer models and self-attention techniques [Vas+17], which overcame the limitations that the RNN and LSTM models faced with long-range dependencies. The self-attention technique allows Transformers to dynamically assign importance to different parts of the input sequence, enabling the model to capture complex contextual relationships. Then, the introduction of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [Dev+19] marks a notable advancement by employing bidirectional context, which contrasts with traditional models that process text sequentially from left to right or from right to left. By considering text in both directions simultaneously, BERT captures a deeper and more detailed understanding of language. Built on the Transformer architecture [Vas+17], BERT is pre-trained using two primary tasks: Masked Language Modeling (MLM) and Next Sentence Prediction (NSP). MLM involves predicting masked words within a sentence, allowing the model to learn from the context of surrounding words. NSP requires predicting whether one sentence logically follows another, which helps the model to understand sentence relationships. This comprehensive pre-training enables BERT to be fine-tuned for a wide range of NLP tasks.

The emergence of LLMs has greatly expanded the capabilities of Image Captioning, allowing richer contextual understanding [RN18; Bro+20]. These models are exceptionally large, with billions of parameters that allow them to effectively capture complex language patterns. Built on the Transformer architecture [Vas+17], they leverage a self-attention mechanism to identify and prioritize contextual relationships between words in a sentence. The development of LLMs typically involves two stages: pre-training and fine-tuning. During pre-training, the model learns from extensive text data, building a broad understanding of language and assimilating knowledge across diverse domains. This is followed by fine-tuning on smaller, task-specific datasets, which refines the model's capabilities for specialized tasks such as language translation or sentiment analysis, further enhancing its performance in these areas [Wei+21; Bro+20]. Moreover, Visual Language Models (VLMs) [Zha+23a] combine visual and textual data to enhance the generation of captions, offering a more unified method of interpreting images. In contrast, MLLMs distinguish themselves as more comprehensive models due to their capability to handle various modalities, including images, text, audio, and others. This multi-faceted processing further enhances captioning systems across a broader spectrum of applications [Tsa+19]. While VLMs primarily focus on aligning image and text modalities through pretraining tasks like contrastive learning and image-text matching, MLLMs integrate both text and visual inputs with a unified pretraining approach. This enables MLLMs to handle a broader range of multimodal tasks and perform complex reasoning across different modalities, extending beyond just image and text. The term *MLLMs* will be used throughout the thesis, as the models used in this work are referred to as MLLMs in the bibliography.

Typical MLLM architectures, as depicted in Figure 2.4, comprise three primary components: a pre-trained LLM backbone that engages with the user, one or more frozen pre-trained visual encoders providing visual information, and an adapter that translates visual embeddings into the text feature space [Caf+24; Wu+23]. The LLM remains frozen to preserve its linguistic knowledge acquired from extensive text data, while the emphasis shifts to adapting the visual components. The visual encoder extracts features from images and conveys them to the LLM through the adapter. Adapters vary in complexity, ranging from simple architectures like MLPs to more sophisticated Transformer-based models such as the Q-Former [Li+23]. MLPs, being computationally efficient, are well-suited for scenarios where the visual encoder is frozen during training, as they introduce fewer parameters. In contrast, the Q-Former employs self-attention and cross-attention mechanisms to enable deeper interactions between visual and textual modalities, using learnable queries to enhance alignment. The LLM then combines both textual and visual information to generate the caption. Finally, the dotted arrow, which bypasses the adapter and connects visual embeddings directly to the LLM, highlights scenarios where the visual embeddings are already compatible for integration with the LLM.

The MLLM is provided with a prompt directing it to identify unusual elements within an image, and based on this instruction, the LLM generates a textual response. Recent research

[Ala+24; Liu+24b; Dai+24; Lau+24a; Lau+24b] explores two main approaches to integrating visual and textual information. The simplest method involves using a linear mapping to project visual features into a textual embedding space, converting visual data directly into text. Approaches like LLaMA-Adapter [Zha+23b] and FROMAGe [KSF23] often use a single linear layer for this transformation. However, these methods may struggle to capture the full complexity of visual-textual interactions. In contrast, LLaVA-1,5 [Liu+24b] utilizes a two-layer MLP, improving the model’s ability to handle visual-textual integration [Caf+24].

Fig. 2.4: The general architecture of MLLMs consists of a visual encoder, an LLM, and a projector, here referred to as the adapter module that links visual inputs to the textual domain. The process begins with an image being passed through a visual encoder, which generates visual features. These features are then processed by an adapter and combined with the prompt given by the user. The resulting embeddings are fed into the LLM, which generates the response. Figure taken from [Caf+24].

Text generation has been improved with methods like beam search, which is commonly used to select the next word in a sequence. With a beam size of $k=5$, beam search keeps track of the top k candidate sequences at each time step t . These sequences are expanded by evaluating potential next words for each step, calculating the likelihood of each candidate word based on the previous tokens, and selecting the top k sequences with the highest probabilities to continue to the next step $t + 1$. This iterative process continues until either a maximum sequence length is reached or a predefined stopping criterion is satisfied. By keeping multiple candidate sequences throughout the generation, beam search significantly reduces the chances of missing a more accurate caption that might otherwise be overlooked if only a single sequence were considered at each stage. Figure 2.5 depicts the beam search process with a beam size of $k=3$. and each row displays the most probable word given the

prior context, with the red boxes at the base showing the top-rated caption at each stage of decoding.

Moreover, to reduce repetitions in LLMs' outputs and make them less predictable, various forms of sampling can be employed. In detail, sampling means randomly picking the next token w_t in a partially generated sequence $w_{1:t-1}$ according to its conditional probability distribution. More elaborate sampling algorithms have also been proposed, such as top- k sampling [FLD18], top- p or Nucleus sampling [Hol+20], locally typical sampling [Mei+23], truncated sampling [HML22] and conformal nucleus sampling [RGG23]. Last but not least, guided-decoding mechanisms have shown promising results in medical image captioning [Kal+24].

Fig. 2.5: Beam Search minimizes the chance of overlooking the most accurate caption by maintaining a fixed number of the most promising sequences at each step. The red boxes display the highest-scoring word at each decoding phase.

2.2 Diagnostic Captioning

In Diagnostic Captioning (DC), the objective is to analyze medical images such as X-rays or MRIs from a patient's exam and to create a draft report highlighting possible medical issues. It is crucial to understand that these systems are designed to support physicians, not to substitute their skills. As Pavlopoulos et al. [PKA19; Pav+22] explain, while the objectives in this field aren't always clearly defined, they generally focus on three key goals: improving the efficiency of medical departments, reducing diagnostic mistakes, and cutting the costs of medical imaging. Figure 2.6 shows examples of image-diagnostic captions pairs.

Fig. 2.6: Examples of diagnostic captions with their associated images taken from the ImageCLEFmed 2024 dataset [Rüc+24a].

A DC system is not effective when simply describing what is visible in an image, unlike generic image captioning models. For example, traditional retrieval methods, despite their simplicity and lack of text generation, can deliver surprisingly strong performance in DC tasks due to their efficiency in matching queries to existing data [Kou19]. These methods pull captions from similar medical exams, which proves effective because medical reports often follow a structured, template-based format to present their findings. As a result, even simple retrieval-based systems, such as 1-NN (Nearest Neighbor), which retrieves and reuses the caption of the most visually similar image [Liu+19], can exceed more complex systems like Transformer-based or encoder-decoder architectures [PKA19].

Although generic image captioning and DC often utilize similar architectures, with an encoder to process images and a decoder to generate text, there have been significant advances in adapting these methods to the medical domain. Starting with traditional architectures using a CNN-RNN [Shi+16] framework to describe a chest X-Ray based on visual features, different attention mechanisms and hierarchical LSTM [HS97] have been proposed to generate radiology reports [JXX18]. However, most of the reports generated by such works tend to describe normal observations, indicating that these methods have difficulty capturing subtle changes in the image [Yan+22]. Following the introduction of Transformers [Vas+17], a significant development was BioBERT [Lee+19], which builds upon BERT [Dev+19] and is trained using full-text articles from PubMed Central¹. BioBERT proved how enhancements in pre-training and optimization could lead to significant improvements in BERT's performance [NP24]. Around the same time, another important model, ClinicalBERT [HAR20], emerged. While BioBERT focused on the biomedical literature, ClinicalBERT was adapted from the BERT model and fine-tuned specifically on clinical notes from electronic health records, allowing it to better understand patient care contexts. However, the introduction of LLMs and MLLMs has significantly transformed the landscape of the medical field. Given the heavy reliance on visual imaging

¹<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>, Last accessed: 2024-11-30

and multi-modal data, VLMs and MLLMs have gained considerable traction in research. Flamingo [Ala+24], one of the first VLMs, demonstrated significant effectiveness, due to its ability to use few-shot examples [KP23]. Then, one of the innovative MLLMs used in this area was Gemini [Tea+24] and Med-Gemini [Saa+24]. Nevertheless, GPT-4 [Ope+24] has fundamentally reshaped the capabilities of LLMs and MLLMs. Although GPT-4 is not pre-trained on biomedical data, research [Wu+23; Caf+24; CFS24; Yin+24] has demonstrated that it is currently the state-of-the-art model in DC [Clu+23; Nor+23].

2.3 Instruction Tuning

LLMs and MLLMs have demonstrated that In-Context Learning (ICL), which involves adding example outputs at the start of a prompt [Bro+20], can greatly improve performance, especially in new tasks. This is made possible by providing task descriptions for each training instance, a technique commonly associated with Instruction Tuning (IT) [Chu+24; Zha+23c]. In addition to pre-training, these models undergo a second phase of training on datasets consisting of

$$(INSTRUCTION, OUTPUT) \tag{2.1}$$

pairs in a supervised manner, where *INSTRUCTION* represents human instructions to the model, and *OUTPUT* is the corresponding desired result. This approach helps bridge the gap between the model's pre-training objective of next-word prediction and the user's goal of having models follow human instructions. LLMs are typically trained to minimize the error in predicting contextual words across large corpora, while users expect the model to follow their instructions. IT makes the model's behavior more controllable and predictable compared to standard LLMs. It is also more computationally efficient, enabling LLMs to quickly adapt to specific domains without having to undergo extensive pre-training or changes to their architecture. By training models on a diverse set of instructions, this method improves the adaptability and effectiveness of both LLMs and MLLMs [Don+24].

MLLMs can take images as input, which leads to more diverse content and requires more complex fine-tuning. Liu et al. [Liu+24b] showed that fine-tuning methods that are effective for LLMs can also enhance the few-shot and zero-shot capabilities of MLLMs. In typical multi-modal instruction samples, there is often an optional directive accompanied by a pair of input and output. This directive is generally a natural language sentence that outlines the task and specifies the model's role, such as:

“You are an experienced medical professor. Try to describe the medical image.”

The input may include both image and text or just an image, with the output representing the model’s response to the given instruction. Formally, a multi-modal instruction example can be represented as a triplet:

$$(I, M, R) \tag{2.2}$$

where I denotes the instruction, M signifies the multi-modal input, and R is the correct response. MLLMs generate an answer based on the instruction and multi-modal input as:

$$A = f(I, M; \theta) \tag{2.3}$$

where A is the predicted answer and θ represents the model’s parameters. The training objective usually follows the original auto-regressive objective used when training LLMs, defined as:

$$L(\theta) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(R_i | I, M, R_{<i}; \theta) \tag{2.4}$$

Where N denotes the length of the ground truth response, and $R_{<i}$ refers to the sequence of tokens in R before the i -th token, representing the context the model has already seen or generated before predicting the i -th token [Yin+24].

Figure 2.7 shows diagnostic captions generated by GPT-4o [Ope+24] during inference on the same image with different prompts. LLaVA 1.5 [Liu+24a], an IT-trained MLLM, has been used to generate these captions. The findings indicate that the BERTScore [Zha+19], utilized to measure the similarity between actual and generated captions (Section 5.1.3), demonstrates better quality in the generated captions when the prompts are more specific, compared to the original captions. In particular, the BERTScore stands at 52% when there is no prompt. This score increases to 62% with a basic prompt, and further improves to 71% when the prompt is highly detailed, encompassing both role and audience. This highlights the importance of prompt design in the generative process, where well-structured and thorough prompts lead to more informative and accurate image captions [Wan+24].

2.4 Efficient Tuning Techniques

Fine-tuning large models with billions of parameters can be highly resource-intensive. To tackle this challenge, Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) methods, such as quantization and low-rank adaptation, are frequently employed. Quantization techniques convert from high-precision formats, such as 32-bit floating-point numbers, to more efficient ones such as 8-bit integers. Precision refers to the number of bits used to represent the model’s parameters and activations. Higher precision ensures more accurate representations and calculations, while lower precision reduces memory usage and speeds up computations, though it may compromise accuracy.

Fig. 2.7: Diagnostic captions generated by GPT-4o for the same image using enhanced, more detailed prompts, showcasing how prompt refinement can improve caption quality.

2.4.1 LoRA

Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [Hu+22] is a technique that significantly decreases the number of trainable parameters by utilizing a low-rank approximation for weight updates. Instead of modifying the entire weight matrix W , which can be computationally expensive, LoRA represents the weight update as follows:

$$\Delta W = AB^T \tag{2.5}$$

where A and B are low-rank matrices with reduced dimensions. Equation 2.5 provides an intuitive approach by breaking down the weight update into smaller, manageable parts. Rather than altering the entire weight matrix W , which consists of $m \times n$ parameters, LoRA utilizes A to signify the update within a reduced-dimensional space, and B to bring it back into the original space. LoRA is more parameter-efficient than unfreezing parts of the network, as it minimizes the number of trainable parameters while retaining the pre-trained knowledge. It also enables targeted, low-rank adaptations without altering the entire weight matrix, helping to prevent overfitting and ensuring stability. If A has dimensions $m \times r$ and B has dimensions $n \times r$, where r is a hyperparameter significantly smaller than both m and n , the resulting total number of trainable parameters is:

$$(m \times r) + (n \times r) \tag{2.6}$$

These are notably fewer than the original $m \times n$ parameters of W . By selecting r to be much smaller, the training costs are minimized while still allowing for adequate model adaptability. Importantly, the original weight matrix W remains unchanged during training, with only the smaller matrices A and B being adjusted, thereby enhancing computational efficiency.

2.4.2 QLoRa

Quantized LoRA (QLoRA) [Det+24] builds upon the foundations of LoRA by combining low-rank adaptation with quantization for further optimization. Similar to LoRA, QLoRA employs the low-rank approximation described in Equation 2.5, but it goes a step further by quantizing the matrices A and B , thereby reducing their precision. This quantization process reduces memory requirements and computational demands, enabling fine-tuning of large models on hardware with limited resources. While the number of trainable parameters remains the same as indicated in Equation 2.6, the use of quantized low-rank matrices significantly boosts the efficiency of the model. By leaving the original weight matrix W unaltered, QLoRA maintains much of the knowledge of the pre-trained model while integrating updates using lower-precision quantized versions of the weight parameters. This approach reduces memory consumption and speeds up computations, allowing for efficient fine-tuning without the need for extensive computational resources.

Methods

This section outlines the methods and systems employed throughout this thesis, with a focus on the ImageCLEFmedical 2024 competition [Ion+24; Rüc+24a], in which we secured the 4th place in the caption generation sub-task out of 11 participating research groups. Sections 3.1 and 3.2 describe different approaches for fine-tuning an LLM on a specific dataset. Section 3.3 introduces an improved system that enhances the draft captions using retrieved information, while the system discussed in Section 3.4 was implemented in order to combine various captions to generate a new one.

3.1 InstructBLIP

InstructBLIP [Dai+24] is a Vision-Language instruction-tuning model that enhances the capabilities of BLIP-2 [Li+23], focusing on following user instructions. As shown in Figure 3.1, both models consist of a ViT encoder (see Figure 2.3), a Querying Transformer (Q-Former) [Li+23], and an LLM. InstructBLIP uses either Vicuna [Chi+23] or FLAN-T5 [Chu+24] as its LLM component. During training, the weights of the image encoder and the LLM are kept frozen as mentioned in Section 2.1. The image encoder generates high-dimensional embeddings from images, while the Q-Former, consisting of two Transformer blocks [Vas+17] with shared self-attention layers, facilitates the transmission of visual information to the LLM. The LLM performs generation tasks by processing both visual features and textual prompts, utilizing learnable queries—trainable parameters that enhance the model’s ability to integrate multimodal inputs. These queries refine their representations through self-attention layers and serve as intermediaries in the cross-attention mechanism, linking visual features from the image encoder with the textual context processed by the LLM [Zha+23c].

InstructBLIP [Dai+24] enhances the Q-Former (Section 2.1) from BLIP-2 [Li+23] by incorporating IT, enabling it to understand textual instructions. Unlike BLIP, which lacked IT and was limited to aligning visual and textual modalities, the Q-Former processes both learnable query embeddings (k) and token embeddings from the textual instruction. These inputs are jointly utilized within its self-attention layers to extract task-relevant visual features. The Q-Former [Dai+24] undergoes two-stage pre-training with image-caption pairs. First, it aligns with the vision encoder to extract meaningful visual features. In the second stage, it integrates with the LLM, blending visual and textual information seamlessly. To

ensure compatibility with the LLM, the output embeddings from the Q-Former are adjusted and concatenated with instruction embeddings, creating a unified representation. This integration enables the model to generate outputs that accurately reflect the combined visual and textual context. As shown in Figure 3.1, cross-attention layers facilitate interaction between instruction-aware embeddings and the image encoder's output. The resulting visual embeddings are projected through a linear layer and combined with the instruction input for the LLM, which generates textual outputs based on the integrated visual features and task details.

Fig. 3.1: The InstructBLIP architecture processes image embeddings to generate responses based on instructions. The Q-Former extracts instruction-aware visual features from the frozen image encoder's output and feeds them as soft prompts to the frozen LLM. It uses self-attention and cross-attention mechanisms to facilitate the interaction between the image features and the instructions, guiding the model to produce relevant responses to queries about the input image. Figure taken by [Dai+24]

3.2 LLaVA

The Large Language and Vision Assistant (LLaVA) [Liu+24b] is an innovative open-source model that combines the CLIP-ViT [Xu+23] vision encoder to extract visual embeddings from images with the Vicuna [Chi+23] as the LLM, enabling a deep understanding of both visual and text embeddings. Figure 3.2 illustrates the LLaVA network architecture, where the LLM, denoted as $f_\phi(\cdot)$ with parameters ϕ , processes the language instructions H_q . The output of the LLM is represented by X_a . The model is fine-tuned through a multi-step process, starting with a pre-trained LM on a large text corpus and then further fine-tuned for specific tasks using IT (Section 2.3).

Fig. 3.2: The LLaVA architecture incorporates a vision encoder that derives visual embeddings Z_v from the input image X_v . These embeddings are transformed into a latent space H_v using a projection matrix W . Concurrently, a language instruction X_q is mapped to H_q . Both H_v and H_q are then processed by the LM f_ϕ to generate the language response X_a . Figure taken from [Liu+24b].

For any given input image X_v , the visual encoder extracts relevant features, represented mathematically as:

$$Z_v = g(X_v) \quad (3.1)$$

These visual features are then transformed into language embedding tokens through a linear layer equipped with a trainable projection matrix W :

$$H_v = W \cdot Z_v \quad (3.2)$$

For each image X_v , a series of question-answer pairs is generated by synthetic users through a back-and-forth interaction with the image, with each new question building upon the previous exchange to form a multi-turn conversation. The conversation is represented as:

$$(X_1^q, X_1^a, \dots, X_T^q, X_T^a) \quad (3.3)$$

where T represents the total number of interactions between the user and the model during the conversation. Each individual turn t , consisting of a question and its corresponding answer, is formatted as follow:

$$X_t^{\text{instruct}} = \begin{cases} \text{Randomly choose } [X_1^q, X_v] \text{ or } [X_v, X_1^q], & \text{for } t = 1 \\ X_t^q, & \text{for } t > 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

According to the authors [Liu+24b], the random selection of a question and its corresponding answer from the list is designed to introduce variety in the generated responses, enabling the model to explore different aspects of the image.

The IT process for the LM is performed on the predicted tokens, applying the standard auto-regressive training objective. In a sequence with a length L , defined as the total count

of tokens comprising visual features, instructions, and target answers, the probability of the target answers X_a is determined as follows:

$$p(X_a | X_v, X_{\text{instruct}}) = \prod_{i=1}^L p_{\theta}(t_i | X_v, X_{\text{instruct}}, t_1, \dots, t_{i-1}, X_a) \quad (3.5)$$

where θ represents the trainable parameters, and $X_{\text{instruct}}, t_1, \dots, t_{i-1}$, and X_a are the instruction tokens, the previously generated tokens up to turn $i - 1$, and the target answer tokens, respectively. These components help the model predict the current token t_i .

A two-stage instruction-tuning procedure is employed to train the LLaVA model [Liu+24b]. During the first stage, the model is pre-trained on image-text pairs, with the multi-modal projector (Figure 2.4) being the only component that is trainable. For an image X_v , a question X_q is randomly sampled to construct X_t^{instruct} . This question acts as a language instruction that asks the assistant to briefly describe the image, with the ground-truth answer X_a being the original caption. During this phase, the weights of both the visual encoder and the LLM remain frozen, maximizing the likelihood given in Equation 3.5. This approach ensures that the image features H_v are effectively aligned with the word embeddings of the pre-trained LLM. In the second stage, the model is fine-tuned, with the visual encoder weights remaining frozen while the pre-trained weights of the LM are updated. According to the authors [Liu+24b], two specific use case scenarios are examined: the first involves fine-tuning a multi-modal chatbot using a dataset of 158K language-image instruction-following pairs [Liu+24b], and the second uses the ScienceQA benchmark [Lu+22], a large-scale multi-modal science question dataset annotated with detailed lectures and explanations. Although LLaVA [Liu+24b] has not publicly disclosed the exact datasets used for training, common datasets for such purposes include MS COCO [Lin+14], which contains 328K images with 2,5 million labeled objects; the Conceptual Captions 3M (CC3M) dataset [Sha+18], comprising 3M images paired with captions collected from the web; and the LAION family [Sch+24], which offers an extensive collection of non-curated image-text pairs sourced from web pages [Caf+24].

3.2.1 LLaVA 1.5

LLaVA-1.5 [Liu+24a] builds upon the original LLaVA [Liu+24b] model, incorporating several significant enhancements. Liu et al. [Liu+24a] discovered that the fully connected vision-language connector in the original model was surprisingly effective and efficient, even with a relatively small amount of training data. This reduced data dependency is vital, as it enables the model to achieve state-of-the-art results without relying on massive datasets. To further improve the model, they upgraded the connector by implementing a two-layer MLP, which enhances its ability to more effectively integrate and process visual and textual information. Key improvements also include the integration of the CLIP-ViT-L-

336px encoder¹, along with additional fine-tuning using Visual Question Answering (VQA) data, further improving its performance. This encoder, which accepts 336×336 images and provides the highest resolution at the time, enables the model to detect subtle differences and contextual details, leading to a more nuanced understanding of visual content. Liu et al. [Liu+24a] demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach, showing improved performance on tasks requiring fine-grained perception, such as Optical Character Recognition (OCR) in the MM-Vet benchmark [Yu+23] and generating detailed descriptions in the LLaVA-Bench-in-the-Wild benchmark [Liu+24b]. These results suggest that the model is better equipped to process fine-grained visual information. Additionally, the higher resolution reduces hallucinations—instances where the model generates inaccurate or fabricated information—by providing clearer details. Moreover, the introduction of LLaVA-1.5-HD [Liu+24a], which increases the resolution to 448×448 , further boosts performance, particularly in tasks that rely heavily on fine details. These findings underscore the crucial role of higher resolution in improving the model’s visual understanding. The integration of visual and textual data is improved by the MLP connector, which aligns the outputs from both the vision encoder and the LLM into a shared space. This two-layer MLP improves upon the simpler single linear layer used in the original LLaVA [Liu+24b], enhancing the alignment of data from different modalities and ensuring more effective comparison and integration. During training, the MLP learns to capture relationships between visual and textual features, improving the model’s performance in tasks like image captioning and visual question answering. Unlike the Q-Former in InstructBLIP (Section 3.1), which requires substantial computational resources for pre-training, the MLP is a simpler structure that is trained on much less data, showcasing its data efficiency [Liu+24a]. Furthermore, fine-tuning the model with VQA data significantly enhances its language capabilities. VQA data, which includes a variety of questions and answers related to visual content, enables the model to generate more effective responses based on visual input.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the architecture of the LLaVA-1.5 model. At the top, Vicuna v1.5 13B [Chi+23] is the LLM used, generating responses based on the instruction prompt. The vision-language connector, implemented with an MLP, integrates visual information with the LLM, while the vision encoder processes the visual input. The user prompt asks about the unusual aspects of the image, demonstrating the system’s ability to answer questions related to visual content.

3.3 Synthesizer

The Synthesizer, a component introduced in this work, is built on the idea that images sharing similar visual features tend to have corresponding captions with similar content.

¹<https://huggingface.co/openai/clip-vit-large-patch14-336>, Last Accessed: 2024-11-30

Fig. 3.3: The architecture of the LLaVA-1.5 model using the Vicuna v1.5 13B as the LM component at the top, an MLP for integrating visual information, and the CLIP ViT-L vision encoder for processing images, all designed to respond to user queries about visual content. Figure taken from [Liu+24a]

The goal of this system is to improve caption quality by utilizing the information embedded within these images. To identify such image similarity, a CNN-FFNN (Feed-Forward Neural Network) model [Sam+24] is employed to extract high-dimensional image embeddings (Section 3.3.1). When the cosine similarity between two embeddings exceeds a certain threshold, the images are classified as neighbors. Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) techniques [Lew+20; Gao+24] are leveraged within the Synthesizer to gather information from these neighboring images and their captions, thereby enriching the caption generation process. Subsequently, the LLaMA-3.1 model² (Section 3.3.2) is employed as a secondary step to refine the initial draft captions generated by another model. This refinement process involves incorporating visual features from neighboring images alongside the textual information from their corresponding captions. Through this method, the model seeks to improve the overall quality of the generated descriptions.

3.3.1 Image Embeddings

Enhancing multi-modal representations using features extracted by deep CNNs has been a key area of research over the past decade [KB14]. In the biomedical field, humans can easily differentiate between similar and dissimilar images, such as those that depict the same medical modality or organ. To enable systems to recognize image similarity, a common approach is to compare features, also known as image embeddings. A widely adopted architecture for extracting these embeddings is the CNN-FFNN framework [ON15; BG94], where a CNN encoder acts as the backbone, followed by an FFNN classification head. The classification task in this framework is designed to facilitate the learning of meaningful embeddings by requiring the model to capture relevant features of the images

²<https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct>, Last Accessed: 2024-11-30

in order to perform the classification accurately. A variety of such tasks can be employed, including object classification, face recognition, or anomaly detection, each focusing on different aspects of the image content. The image features are typically drawn from the final convolutional layer of the CNN encoder. Figure 3.4 provides a visual representation of this process.

Fig. 3.4: Illustration of a CNN-FFNN architecture, where a radiology image serves as the input. This image is processed through a series of convolutional and pooling layers to extract feature embeddings before being fed into the classification head.

The image embeddings are used to find similar images with the k -NN (k -Nearest Neighbors) algorithm. For each test image, the CNN encoder generates the corresponding embeddings, which the k -NN algorithm uses to retrieve similar images from the training set based on cosine similarity [HKP12]. To classify two images as similar, their cosine similarity, which measures the cosine of the angle between the embeddings (Equation 3.6), must exceed a specified threshold. Higher values indicate greater similarity.

$$\text{cosine_similarity}(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) = \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{B}\|} \quad (3.6)$$

where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are the image embeddings.

Figure 3.5 illustrates the architecture of the Synthesizer system. The model used may vary, but its objective is to generate a single caption for an image by merging captions from images that are visually similar. The input image, which has dimensions of 224×224 , is processed through the Embeddings Model, specifically the CNN-FFNN framework described in Section 3.3.1. This processing was previously applied to all images in the dataset [Rüc+24a] to enable the retrieval of neighboring images. The Synthesizer integrates the visual embeddings from the input image as well as those from neighboring images, using their corresponding captions to provide context. Multiple embeddings are extracted from a single image because different regions or features of the image are represented individually, with each one capturing a unique aspect of the visual content. The Synthesizer utilizes this information by drawing from the visual representation of the test image, the data from the neighboring images, and their corresponding captions to synthesize the final caption.

Fig. 3.5: The Synthesizer architecture retrieves neighboring images through their embeddings and uses them, along with the embeddings of the input image and draft caption, to generate the final caption guided by the prompt.

3.3.2 Llama 3.1 Instruct

Llama-3.1 [Gra+24], used as the Synthesizer system in Figure 3.5, is a widely used LLM trained in two stages. During the pre-training stage, the model learns the language and builds foundational knowledge, while the post-training stage focuses on fine-tuning the model to follow instructions. The model has undergone fine-tuning through both Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) and Reinforcement Learning with Human Feedback (RLHF) to better align its capabilities with human preferences for both helpfulness and safety [Gra+24].

Despite LLaMA-3.1 [Gra+24] was not originally designed for image processing, researchers modified it by incorporating a pretrained Vision Encoder [Xu+23] alongside cross-attention layers [Ala+24]. This modification enables the model to process visual information effectively, integrating it with the LLM's capabilities. The approach consists of four key stages: language model pre-training, multi-modal encoder pre-training, vision adapter training and model fine-tuning. The image encoder is trained on a large number of image-text pairs, allowing the model to learn the relationship between visual content and its natural language description. During the vision adapter training stage, cross-attention layers are introduced between the visual token representations generated by the image encoder and the token representations produced by the LLM. These layers are inserted after every fourth self-attention layer in the core language model [Ala+24]. The model fine-tuning stage

focuses on adapting the pre-trained model for specific downstream tasks, emphasizing the importance of selecting an appropriate data mix and ensuring data quality.

As illustrated in Figure 3.6, the model processes a single image by splitting it into patches, which are then fed into the ViT encoder [Dos+21]. This encoder utilizes self-attention and a feedforward network to generate a representation for each patch. The encoder’s outputs, representing each image patch, are then aggregated to form the final Image Embeddings. In parallel, the LLM processes the text input, which is transformed into Token Embeddings through self-attention and feedforward layers. Cross-Attention mechanisms then allow the LLM to integrate information from both the image and text. Through this process, the Image Embeddings interact with the Token Embeddings, enabling the model to generate a text output based on the combined information from both modalities. This process is iterative, with the generated output contributing to the input for the subsequent token prediction. The cycle continues until the model outputs a special end-of-sequence token or reaches a predefined output length.

Fig. 3.6: Overview of the LLaMA-3.1 pipeline, where image patches and text inputs are encoded separately, and their embeddings are integrated through cross-attention to generate a text output. Figure adapted from [Gra+24].

LLaMA-3.1 serves as the Synthesizer, processing the test image along with the draft caption, as well as neighboring images identified through embedding similarity and their corresponding captions. These inputs are concatenated into a single sequence before being fed into the model (Section 3.3) [Sam+24; Kal+23; Cha+22]). Guided by a specific prompt designed to make the LLM integrate visual and textual information, the model effectively refines the draft caption as shown in Figure 3.5. Figure 3.7 shows a test image along with an initial caption generated by LLaVA-1.5 (Section 3.2.1). It also includes the neighboring image with its corresponding caption and the final caption produced by the Synthesizer. For comparison purposes, the gold caption is presented. Yellow highlights within each

caption highlight the similarities to the gold caption. As shown, the initial caption shares similarities with the gold caption, correctly identifying the modality and referencing the arrows. The initial caption shares similarities with the gold caption, correctly identifying the modality and referencing the arrows. The Synthesizer builds on this by incorporating visual information from both the test image and the neighboring image, along with its caption, resulting in a more detailed and comprehensive final caption. The final caption accurately identifies congestion in the region marked by the red arrow and explains that the ground-glass opacities, derived from the neighboring image, may indicate pleural effusion, as noted in the gold caption. However, despite these improvements, the final caption still does not match the accuracy of the gold standard.

Fig. 3.7: The test image is shown with its initial caption, alongside the neighboring image and its respective caption. The final caption highlights the model’s use of both visual and textual information from the neighboring image. The gold caption is also provided for reference. Images and the original caption are taken from [Rüc+24a].

3.4 MLLM Ensembling

Recent studies [Ver+24; JRL23] have increasingly concentrated on fine-tuning more efficient LMs for task completion, driven by the significant costs, resource demands, and time involved in training larger models. This section explores how training a compact LM to combine captions from various MLLMs can lead to the generation of more accurate and detailed medical captions [Ver+24; JRL23]. This concept is influenced by the idea that, in many cases, clinicians seek multiple consultations to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the patient’s condition. In this process, the captions of LLaVA-1.5 (Section 3.2.1), LLaMA-3.1 (Section 3.3.2) and Idefics2 (Section 3.4.1) are used. Then a FLAN-T5 model (Section 3.4.2) is used to combine these captions and produce a more concise output. This strategy relies solely on the outputs of the MLLMs to enhance performance while also eliminating the need to access their underlying weights [Ver+24].

3.4.1 Idefics2

Idefics2³ [Lau+24b] is a VLM designed to process and generate text based on visual input. The training of VLMs typically involves the integration of a pre-trained vision backbone with a pre-trained language backbone. This initial phase requires large multi-modal datasets, especially image-caption pairs. For this phase, Idefics2 was trained on a diverse range of publicly available datasets, including OBELICS [Lau+24a], the Public Multi-modal Dataset⁴, and LAION-COCO [Sch+24]. Following pre-training, a stage akin to instruction tuning is employed, where the model is trained on task-specific examples. The authors created and utilized a multi-modal instruction fine-tuning dataset named The Cauldron⁵, which consists of 50 carefully selected datasets designed for conversations involving multiple exchanges between the user and the model. This dataset encompasses a variety of tasks, including visual question answering and image captioning in a question-and-answer format [Wei+21].

As discussed in Section 3.3.2, the LLaMA-3.1 model [Gra+24] employs a *cross-attention architecture* [Lau+24a; Ala+24], which is also used in the predecessor of Idefics2 [Lau+24a]. In this architecture, images encoded by the vision backbone are integrated at various layers within the LM through interleaved cross-attention blocks, allowing the text to cross-attend to the hidden states of the images. In contrast, Section 3.2.1 details how LLaVa-1.5 [Lau+24b] utilizes a different approach known as the *fully-autoregressive architecture*. In this method, the output from the vision encoder is directly concatenated with the sequence of text embeddings, forming a combined input sequence of visual and text tokens for the LM. Laurençon et al. [Lau+24b] found that the cross-attention architecture outperforms the fully-autoregressive method when uni-modal pre-trained backbones are kept frozen. Figure 3.8 illustrates the fully-autoregressive architecture of Idefics2 [Lau+24b]. In this setup, an image of up to 980×980 pixels is processed by a vision encoder that extracts hidden feature representations. These features are then passed through a modality projection and pooling layer to prepare them for integration with the LLM. Ultimately, the text embeddings T_T are concatenated with the visual tokens before being fed into the LLM.

3.4.2 FLAN-T5

Fine-tuned LAnguage Net T5 (FLAN-T5) [Chu+24] is an advanced open-source sequence-to-sequence language model that builds on the Transformer architecture [Vas+17] and extends the capabilities of the T5 model (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) [Raf+20]. Following the text-to-text framework, FLAN-T5 treats every NLP task as a problem of

³<https://huggingface.co/HuggingFaceM4/idefics2-8b>, Last Accessed: 2024-11-30

⁴<https://huggingface.co/datasets/facebook/pmd>, Last Accessed: 2024-11-30

⁵https://huggingface.co/datasets/HuggingFaceM4/the_cauldron, Last Accessed: 2024-11-30

Fig. 3.8: Architecture of IdeFics2. The model integrates concatenated visual tokens and text embeddings, represented by the green and red columns, respectively. Figure adapted from [Lau+24b].

converting one piece of text into another, similar to its predecessor T5. This approach allows it to handle a wide variety of tasks in a unified manner, including translation, summarization and question-answering [Raf+20; Chu+24]. FLAN-T5 undergoes extensive pre-training on a large and diverse text corpus, allowing it to develop a deep understanding of language. What truly distinguishes FLAN-T5 is its IT (Section 2.3), which allows it to follow more complex language instructions than its predecessor. This enhancement significantly improves its ability to adapt to new tasks. As a result, FLAN-T5 shows impressive performance improvements on various benchmarks. Figure 3.9 illustrates several examples of how FLAN-T5 [Chu+24] transforms various tasks into the text-to-text framework.

Fig. 3.9: Prompting examples for FLAN-T5, featuring several Instruction Tuning [Zha+23c] and Chain-of-Thought [Wei+24] demonstrations that illustrate the model's prompting and reasoning processes. Figure taken from [Chu+24].

3.4.3 LM-Fuser

Improving the performance of LLMs without relying on fine-tuning, few-shot learning, or similar techniques is a significant challenge. Vernikos et al. [Ver+24] proposed a promising solution to this issue, focusing on optimizing LLM outputs without needing access to the model weights. Predictions from three different MLLMs were combined, and a fine-tuned FLAN-T5 model, called LM-Fuser, was developed to merge these predictions. LM-Fuser has the advantage of requiring only a single pass through the LLM and, by training multiple candidates for the same sequence, it mitigates the risk of overfitting [Ver+24]. This approach was influenced by the tendency of clinicians to seek second opinions in order to decide on the best course of action for a patient's subsequent medical examinations. Since different medical professionals may have varying perspectives, combining their observations can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the medical state of the patient. The objective is to generate captions that facilitate the training of the more efficient LM in combining various candidate captions into a single output that more closely aligns with the gold caption. LM-Fuser is built on the concept that MLLMs can generate captions effectively without needing extensive fine-tuning on a specific dataset, as they leverage the knowledge gained during their initial pre-training, which is further enhanced by the prompts given. Therefore, FLAN-T5 (Section 3.4.2) is trained to combine multiple candidate outputs for the same input, thereby improving its ability to generate more accurate captions. This approach helps reduce the costs usually associated with fine-tuning MLLMs. The process is illustrated in Figure 3.10, where the MLLMs first generate captions for each image, producing alternative captions for both the training and validation sets. These datasets are then used to train the LM-Fuser, enabling it to integrate the generated information and produce the final captions, without the need to directly view the image.

Fig. 3.10: An illustration of LM-Fuser, which utilizes the outputs from multiple MLLMs to generate a more concise caption by integrating the various candidate predictions.

Data

This section provides an overview and explores the ImageCLEFmedical 2024 dataset through an exploratory data analysis [Rüc+24a]. This dataset was used throughout the course of this thesis in order to evaluate the performance and efficiency of the developed systems, which are described in Section 3.

4.1 ImageCLEFmedical 2024

The ImageCLEFmedical 2024 [Rüc+24a] is a subset of the Radiology Objects in COntext (ROCO) dataset [Pel+18]. It consists of 80,080 biomedical images, each accompanied by their associated medical concepts (tags) in the form of UMLS terms¹[Bod04], as well as a brief diagnostic caption. Figure 4.1 illustrates an image alongside its diagnostic caption, the corresponding CUIs, and their matched tags. The dataset is divided into two subsets, each addressing a different task: Concept Detection and Caption Prediction. In the Concept Detection task, the objective is to identify the distinct medical concepts (tags) depicted in each image, while the Caption Prediction task aims to generate a medical diagnosis using an open-ended approach.

The training and validation subsets provided by ImageCLEFmedical 2024 [Ion+24] were combined into a single set, which was then divided into three subsets: training, validation, and development (private test set). This re-splitting was carried out in a stratified manner, following a 75% – 10% – 15% ratio, to ensure the development set (private test set) intended for evaluation purposes is consistent with the entire training set. Consequently, a total of 64,928 images were obtained as training data, 7,179 images were designated for the validation set, and the remaining 7,973 images were allocated to the held-out development set. Subsequently, the hidden official test set was made available for evaluation. This dataset utilizes the Radiology Objects in COntext Version 2 (ROCOv2) [Rüc+24b], which is an enhanced and expanded iteration of the original ROCO dataset [Pel+18]. It contains 17,237 previously unseen images, ensuring an unbiased assessment of the performance of the models.

¹UMLS: <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/index.html>, Last accessed: 2024-11-30

Fig. 4.1: An example taken from [Rüc+24a], showing a biomedical image, its diagnostic caption, associated CUIs, and the corresponding tags matched to the CUIs.

4.1.1 Concept Detection

Concept Detection is a multi-label classification problem that involves identifying 1,945 distinct biomedical concepts, derived from UMLS [Bod04]. The objective of this sub-task is to identify the specific medical concepts (tags) present in each image. Among the available concepts (tag set), four correspond to specific imaging modalities: "X-Ray Computed Tomography", "Ultrasonography", "Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)", and "Computed Tomography (CT) scans". All concepts are represented by Concept Unique Identifiers (CUIs) according to the UMLS standard. The distribution of concepts is highly imbalanced, with a few concepts occurring thousands of times, while many others appear in fewer than ten instances. This leads to a skewed *long-tail* distribution of tags, as illustrated in Figure 4.2(a), where the frequencies of the concepts, represented by the number of images associated with each concept, are plotted in descending order against their corresponding class indices. A comprehensive exploratory analysis of this year's dataset indicated that certain concepts are more prevalent (Table 4.1); these typically correspond to types of medical examinations, such as X-ray Computed Tomography or plain X-Ray. The majority of images within the ground truth dataset encompass at least one of these broad concepts, in addition to more detailed ones. The maximum and minimum number of concepts assigned to a single image are 27 and 1, which occur in 1 and 8,567 images, respectively. The average number of

concepts assigned per image is 3,15. These findings are summarized in the histogram shown in Figure 4.2(b).

Fig. 4.2: (a) Visualization of the dataset’s *long-tail* distribution, where the y-axis represents the number of occurrences of each concept, and the x-axis represents the concept’s class index. (b) Histogram with 25 fixed-size bins (horizontal axis) illustrating the number of gold concepts per image. Note that 13 concepts do not have corresponding UMLS terms.

Tab. 4.1: The ten most frequent concepts, along with their CUIs and UMLS terms, from the Image-CLEFmedical2024 dataset [Rüc+24a], and the number of images they are associated with.

Most Common Concepts			
Rank	CUI	UMLS Term	Images
1	C0040405	X-Ray Computed Tomography	27,852
2	C1306645	Plain x-ray	22,104
3	C0024485	Magnetic Resonance Imaging	12,733
4	C0041618	Ultrasonography	11,476
5	C0817096	Chest	10,323
6	C0002978	Angiogram	4,808
7	C0000726	Abdomen	4,292
8	C0037303	Bone structure of cranium	4,130
9	C0030797	Pelvis	3,678
10	C0023216	Lower Extremity	3,254

4.1.2 Caption Prediction

For Caption Prediction, each image is paired with a gold diagnostic caption that describes the medical conditions depicted. The dataset contains a total of 80,080 gold captions, with one assigned to each image. The majority of these captions, specifically 99.47% (79,658 out of 80,080 captions), are unique. An exploratory analysis of the dataset [Rüc+24a] revealed that the longest caption contains 848 words (occurring once), while the shortest

consists of just 1 word (appearing 73 times), with an average caption length of 21,01 words. These statistics apply to the dataset as a whole, and careful verification has been conducted to ensure their consistency across all three subsets (training, validation, and development) that were formed. In Figure 4.3, a histogram (Figure 4.3(a)) and a box plot (Figure 4.3(b)) are presented. These visualizations employ a logarithmic scale, which enhances the visibility of smaller values and reduces the influence of larger ones. This approach provides a clearer understanding of the overall distribution of the data. During training, all captions exceeding 100 words were excluded to encourage the generation of more concise and diagnostic captions while minimizing the potential for hallucinations, which refer to instances of information that is not supported by the input data [Ji+23], produced by the employed MLLMs.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.3: (a) Histogram visualizing the distribution of caption lengths. The y -axis, displayed on a logarithmic scale, represents the number of images falling into each bin, while the x -axis shows the number of words in the captions. (b) Box-plot depicting the same distribution on a logarithmic scale, emphasizing outliers within the range of 100 to 200 words.

The five most frequently occurring captions and the ten most common words, excluding stopwords, are detailed in Tables 4.2 and 4.3, respectively. As expected, the most common

captions are general, offering overarching details about the type of examination. Similarly, the most common words encompass anatomical structures, basic topology, and standard medical examinations.

According to the organizers [Ion+24], each caption is pre-processed before evaluated in the following manner:

- The caption is converted to lower-case.
- Numbers are replaced by words, e.g., number 10 becomes “ten.”
- Punctuation is removed.

Tab. 4.2: The five most common gold captions found in the ImageCLEFmedical2024 dataset [Rüc+24a] alongside the number of images they are associated with.

Most Common Captions		
Rank	Caption	Occurrences
1	Initial panoramic radiograph.	40
2	Final panoramic radiograph.	37
3	Chest X-ray.	20
4	Chest radiograph.	17
5	Preoperative CT scan.	9

Tab. 4.3: The ten most frequently occurring words in the gold captions and their respective frequencies in the ImageCLEFmedical2024 dataset [Rüc+24a], following the removal of stop-words.

Most Common Words (Excluding Stop-Words)	
Word	Count
showing	22,519
right	18,258
left	18,136
ct	15,167
image	10,245
chest	10,082
scan	9,296
computed	9,273
tomography	8,969
shows	8,600

Experiments

This chapter presents the experiments conducted throughout this thesis, including AUEB NLP Group’s participation in the ImageCLEFmedical 2024 competition [Ion+24], as well as the evaluation metrics employed to assess the performance of the developed systems.

5.1 Evaluation Metrics

The automatic evaluation of Natural Language Generation (NLG) involves comparing generated sentences with annotated references to determine semantic equivalence. This thesis employed four evaluation metrics to assess the effectiveness of the diagnostic captions generated by the systems. Each metric offers distinct insights, focusing on different aspects of the evaluation process and allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the quality of the captions.

5.1.1 BLEU

BLEU (BiLingual Evaluation Understudy) [Pap+02] is a widely used metric for assessing the quality of machine-generated text sequences by comparing their word or n -gram overlaps with reference texts. This metric quantifies the overlap of position-independent, matching n -grams between the generated sequence and the reference sequence, with a higher number of matches indicating better quality. BLEU scores range from 0 to 1, with a score of 1 signifying a perfect match. Initially, each n -gram in the reference text can be matched at most once. The number of exact matches is then accumulated for all reference-candidate pairs in the corpus and divided by the total number of n -grams in all candidate sentences. BLEU is typically computed for multiple values of n (e.g., $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$) and the scores are averaged geometrically. Specifically, the precision p_n for each n -gram length n is calculated as:

$$p_n = \frac{\text{number of matching } n\text{-grams}}{\text{total number of candidate } n\text{-grams}} \quad (5.1)$$

The final BLEU score is determined by first computing the geometric mean of the modified precision scores for n -grams up to length N using the formula:

$$\text{Geometric Mean} = \exp \left(\sum_{n=1}^N w_n \log p_n \right) \quad (5.2)$$

where p_n is the precision for each n and w_n represents the weight assigned to each n -gram length.

After calculating the geometric mean, a Brevity Penalty (BP) is applied to account for differences in length between the candidate and reference texts. The BP is defined as:

$$\text{BP} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } c > r, \\ e^{(1-\frac{r}{c})} & \text{if } c \leq r, \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

where c denotes the length of the candidate sequence and r represents the length of the effective reference sequence.

The final BLEU score is then given by:

$$\text{BLEU} = \text{BP} \cdot \exp \left(\sum_{n=1}^N w_n \log p_n \right) \quad (5.4)$$

BLEU is preferred for its simplicity in computation and clear interpretation. However, it has notable limitations. Its strong dependence on n -grams can restrict its ability to capture contextual similarities, which reflect the broader meaning and semantics of the text. Additionally, the BP may penalize longer generated sequences, potentially leading to lower similarity scores, even when these longer sequences are semantically aligned with the reference text.

5.1.2 ROUGE

ROUGE (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation) [Lin04] is another widely used metric for evaluating text generation. It measures the quality of a summary by comparing it to reference summaries created by humans. ROUGE measures the overlap of n -grams, words, or word sequences between the generated text and the reference summaries. Specifically, it calculates the recall of n -grams, which is the ratio of n -grams present in both the generated text and the reference text to the total number of n -grams in the reference text. ROUGE is computed as follows:

$$ROUGE = \sum_n r(n), \quad (5.5)$$

where $r(n)$ indicates the recall for each n -gram length.

The most significant scores computed by ROUGE are ROUGE- N , which evaluates n -gram overlap; ROUGE- L , which examines the longest common subsequence; and ROUGE- S , which assesses skip-bigram co-occurrence statistics [Lin04].

- **ROUGE- N** : The most straightforward among the scores, as it assesses the overlap of n -grams between the generated and reference texts. The N refers to the length of the n -gram being analyzed. For instance, ROUGE-1 evaluates unigram matches, ROUGE-2 focuses on bigram matches, and so forth. ROUGE- N is calculated as:

$$ROUGE-N = \frac{\sum_{S_{\text{ref}} \in \text{Summaries}_{\text{Reference}}} \sum_{n \in \text{gram}_n} \text{Count}_{\text{match}}(n)}{\sum_{S_{\text{ref}} \in \text{Summaries}_{\text{Reference}}} \sum_{n \in \text{gram}_n} \text{Count}(n)}, \quad (5.6)$$

where n stands for the length of the n -gram, $\text{Count}_{\text{match}}(n)$ represents the maximum number of n -grams that occur simultaneously in both the candidate summary and the set of reference summaries.

- **ROUGE- L** : This metric computes the Longest Common Subsequence (LCS) between the candidate and reference summaries. The score is based on the length of the LCS, reflecting the overlap of content between the two texts. ROUGE- L is often considered more effective than ROUGE- N for evaluating semantic similarity, as it focuses on the structure and meaning of the text rather than exact word matches. Unlike ROUGE- N , which relies on n -gram overlap and is sensitive to word order, ROUGE- L captures the common subsequences between the texts without being influenced by the exact arrangement of words.
- **ROUGE- S** : It calculates the overlap of skip-bigrams between the candidate and reference sequences. Skip-bigrams are pairs of words that allow for an arbitrary number of intervening words between them. This method retains some information about word order in the evaluation while offering more flexibility than conventional n -grams.

As previously noted, ROUGE [Lin04] is a recall-based metric. It evaluates how many of the n -grams in the reference summaries are captured by the candidate summary, using the total number of n -grams in the reference summaries as the basis for this calculation. In contrast, BLEU (Section 5.1.1) is a precision-based metric, evaluating the quality of

a candidate sequence by determining the proportion of n -grams in the candidate that overlap with those in the reference translations. However, similar to BLEU [Pap+02], the capabilities of ROUGE scores are also constrained by their inability to effectively capture semantic similarity between the candidate and reference sequences.

5.1.3 BERTScore

BERTScore [Zha+19] is an advanced metric for evaluating the quality of generated text by leveraging context-aware token embeddings from a pretrained BERT (Section 2.1). This metric utilizes BERT [Dev+19] because it can handle rare or Out-Of-Vocabulary (OOV) terms, as well as synonyms and paraphrases, which traditional n -gram overlap methods may overlook. This allows for a more detailed evaluation of the text, capturing subtle variations in meaning. BERTScore calculate similarity scores for each token in the candidate sentence by comparing it with every token in the reference sentence, utilizing the contextual embeddings from BERT. These embeddings generate different vector representations for the same word based on its context. The metric determines sentence similarity by aggregating cosine similarities between the embeddings of the tokens of the two sentences. The calculation employs a greedy matching strategy, pairing each token in the candidate sentence with its most similar counterpart in the reference sentence.

Unlike traditional metrics like ROUGE (Section 5.1.2) and BLEU (Section 5.1.1), which often fail to recognize paraphrasing and impose unfair penalties, BERTScore can identify semantically equivalent phrases with different wording, thus avoiding such issues. It also overcomes the limitations of conventional n -gram models, which often fail to capture distant dependencies and tend to penalize meaningful reordering. Furthermore, BERTScore has shown a high degree of correlation with human judgments in image captioning [YDH20], which is the main subject of the thesis. In contrast to BLEU [Pap+02], which is constrained by a fixed n -gram length, the contextualized embeddings used by BERTScore allow for the capture of dependencies of virtually unlimited length. Consequently, BERTScore has been chosen as the main evaluation metric for this thesis.

For a reference x and a candidate \hat{x} , which represent the word embeddings of the reference and candidate sequences, respectively, three different BERTScores are calculated. Precision (Equation 5.7) is determined by finding the maximum score between each token in \hat{x} and its most similar token in x , normalized by the total number of tokens in \hat{x} . Recall (Equation 5.8) measures the maximum score between each token in x and its most similar token in \hat{x} , normalized by the total number of tokens in x . Finally, F1 (Equation 5.9) combines Precision and Recall using their harmonic mean [Zha+19].

$$P_{\text{BERT}} = \frac{1}{|\hat{x}|} \sum_{\hat{x}_j \in \hat{x}} \max_{x_i \in x} \text{score}(x_i, \hat{x}_j) \quad (5.7)$$

$$R_{\text{BERT}} = \frac{1}{|x|} \sum_{x_i \in x} \max_{\hat{x}_j \in \hat{x}} \text{score}(x_i, \hat{x}_j) \quad (5.8)$$

$$F_{\text{BERT}} = \frac{2 \cdot P_{\text{BERT}} \cdot R_{\text{BERT}}}{P_{\text{BERT}} + R_{\text{BERT}}} \quad (5.9)$$

Figure 5.1 illustrates the calculation of BERTScore. Initially, both the candidate and reference sequences are input into the BERT model to obtain their respective contextual embeddings. Following this, a similarity matrix is constructed by computing the pairwise cosine similarity between each word embedding from the candidate and reference sequences. A higher score signifies a stronger semantic match between specific words in the two sentences.

Fig. 5.1: Illustration of the BERTScore computation process, in which candidate and reference sequences are transformed into contextual embeddings using the BERT model [Dev+19] and compared using pairwise cosine similarity to identify semantic similarity. Figure taken from [Zha+19].

While newer models overcome several limitations of earlier evaluation metrics like BLEU [Pap+02] and ROUGE [Lin04], they also have drawbacks. These models rely on the quality and robustness of the embeddings they generate, and they tend to produce less informative representations for numbers and named entities. [HB21].

5.1.4 BLEURT

BLEURT (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy with Representations from Transformers) [SDP20] is an other evaluation metric that utilizes Transfer Learning (TL) [Zhu+20] techniques. It combines traditional overlap-based metrics, such as BLEU (Section 5.1.1), with the contextual depth offered by Transformer-based embeddings [Vas+17], as seen in BERTScore (Section 5.1.3). This integration allows BLEURT to more effectively capture nuanced semantic similarities between two text sequences. In the initial phase, BLEURT

employs BERT [Dev+19], which is subsequently fine-tuned for the specific evaluation task. To enhance BLEURT’s robustness, the authors introduce a novel pre-training approach in which the model is *warmed up* by training on thousands of synthetic reference-candidate text pairs generated using various noise functions, such as word deletion, applied to freely available web sentences. This approach builds on the original training of BERT. In its initial phase, BLEURT’s performance is assessed using well-established automatic metrics, such as BLEU (Section 5.1.1), offering an initial evaluation of its effectiveness. However, BLEURT’s true potential is realized after this stage, during end-to-end training and fine-tuning with human-assessments, which may be derived from general public datasets, domain-specific datasets, or a combination of both [SDP20].

5.2 Experimental Results

This section provides details on the experiments performed during the implementation of the proposed models discussed in Section 3. It includes information on the experimental setup, data pre-processing steps, and the training process. Fine-tuning was conducted using the training set, while parameter tuning was performed using the validation set. The models were evaluated using the development (private test set) (Section 4).

5.2.1 Prompt Engineering

As discussed in Section 2.3, LLMs and MLLMs are trained to follow specific instructions in their tasks [CLF24; Wan+24]. However, crafting effective prompts is crucial for maximizing their performance. Research highlights that a successful prompt should define both the model’s role (e.g., acting as a medical assistant) and the intended audience, ensuring the use of appropriate language [Whi+23; Sah+24]. Additionally, incorporating few-shot examples can significantly improve the model’s ability to follow patterns and generate more accurate responses [Liu+21; PL22]. Throughout this thesis, a variety of prompts were tested, and the final choices were based on their performance in the validation set (Section 4). Table 5.1 presents a range of prompts provided to LLaVA [Liu+24b] during inference, along with the BERTScores [Zha+19] for the generated captions. The selection process focused on two of the highest-performing prompts, as well as the simplest one, to explore the different impacts that prompt complexity can have on model output. The purpose of this strategy was to deliver an extensive insight into the way diverse prompt structures affect the quality of caption creation. All the experiments were conducted using these selected prompts.

Tab. 5.1: Prompts evaluated in the validation set using LLaVA, along with the BERTScore metrics of the generated captions.

Instruction Prompts and BERTScore		
#	Instruction Prompt	Captions and BERTScore
1	"Describe the radiology image and any significant findings."	55,36
2	"Write a brief caption for the medical image, focusing on any important findings relevant for diagnosis."	55,80
3	"As a healthcare professional, describe this medical image, noting any key features that stand out."	56,40
4	"As an experienced radiologist, you are being given radiology images along with a draft medical diagnosis. Generate a descriptive caption that highlights any significant abnormalities of the radiology image."	57,69
5	"As a medical expert, please provide a detailed caption for the medical image showing [describe the content of the image, e.g., 'an MRI scan of the brain' or 'a histopathology slide of lung tissue']. Include relevant observations, diagnoses if applicable, and any significant findings. Your caption should be clear and concise, aimed at aiding medical professionals in understanding the image's clinical significance."	58,36

5.2.2 Fine Tuning InstructBLIP

InstructBLIP [Dai+24] is a Vision-Language instruction-tuning model developed to efficiently adapt to new tasks using specific training instructions. As discussed in Section 3.1, the system architecture integrates an image encoder, a Q-Former, and an LLM. Both the image encoder and the LLM remain frozen during training, with only the Q-Former being fine-tuned. InstructBLIP was used with FLAN-T5 [Chu+24], as Kaliosis et al. [KP23; Kal+23] demonstrated that FLAN-T5 performs better when used as the backbone model. Beam search was then employed with various beam widths, since the beam width impacts the quality of the generated captions, as discussed in Section 2.1. It was found that $b = 4$ beams yielded the best performance.

Table 5.2 presents the results generated by InstructBLIP [Dai+24] for each prompt. The last and more detailed prompt yielded the best outcomes, supporting the intuition that more specific and well-elaborated prompts lead to better responses.

A novel data-driven guided decoding mechanism was employed to integrate domain-specific information. Specifically, the model learns to incorporate keywords into the text generation process to guide the generation of more relevant text. This method, known as Distance from Median Maximum Concept Similarity (DMMCS) [Kal+24; KP23], operates on the premise that an accurate diagnostic caption should highlight the key medical

Tab. 5.2: Instructions and performance scores for the InstructBLIP model across various prompts.

SFT InstructBLIP - Results					
Instruction Prompts		Performance Metrics			
ID	Instruction	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
1	"Describe the radiology image and any significant findings."	58,18	16,52	24,95	7,1
2	"As an experienced radiologist, you are being given radiology images along with a draft medical diagnosis. Generate a descriptive caption that highlights any significant abnormalities of the radiology image."	59,42	17,35	25,10	8,6
3	"As a medical expert, please provide a detailed caption for the medical image showing [describe the content of the image, e.g., 'an MRI scan of the brain' or 'a histopathology slide of lung tissue']. Include relevant observations, diagnoses if applicable, and any significant findings. Your caption should be clear and concise, aimed at aiding medical professionals in understanding the image's clinical significance."	61,64	19,31	27,85	10,0

conditions depicted in the image. To implement this, the authors used predicted tags from their Concept Detection systems (Section 4.1.2) to guide the Caption Prediction models in generating captions that accurately convey these tags. At each step of the decoding process, a penalty is applied to prioritize words that are semantically aligned with the predicted medical tags. This penalty also takes into account how frequently each tag is represented in the dataset's gold captions, whether explicitly or implicitly. Table 5.3 presents the evaluation metrics for the InstructBLIP-DMMCS system based on the two prompts used [Sam+24].

Tab. 5.3: Instructions and performance scores for InstructBLIP with DMMCS across various prompts.

SFT InstructBLIP with DMMCS - Results					
Instruction Prompts		Performance Metrics			
ID	Instruction	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
1	"Describe the radiology image and any significant findings"	58,34	16,48	25,16	8,3
2	"As an experienced radiologist, you are being given radiology images along with a draft medical diagnosis. Generate a descriptive caption that highlights any significant abnormalities of the radiology image."	60,48	18,25	26,90	10,6
3	"As a medical expert, please provide a detailed caption for the medical image showing [describe the content of the image, e.g., 'an MRI scan of the brain' or 'a histopathology slide of lung tissue']. Include relevant observations, diagnoses if applicable, and any significant findings. Your caption should be clear and concise, aimed at aiding medical professionals in understanding the image's clinical significance."	62,11	20,49	28,99	11,1

5.2.3 Fine Tuning LLaVA 1.5

LLaVA-1.5 [Liu+24a], as mentioned in Section 3.2.1, is an advanced version of the LLaVA model [Liu+24b]. LLaVA-1.5 has 7 billion parameters¹, making its fine-tuning directly expensive in terms of both hardware and time. Therefore, QLoRA (Section 2.4.2) is used and all the following experiments were conducted with an 8-bit quantization of the model. The process involved a batch size of 4, with a maximum of 30 epochs, and employed Early Stopping with a patience threshold of 3 epochs. Table 5.4 presents the metrics (Section 5.1) for beam search applied to each prompt, based on experiments conducted on the validation set (Section 4). The prompts used are the same as those listed in Table 5.3. The results show that the third prompt, combined with a beam size of 4, achieved the best performance. While a beam size of $b = 5$ showed slight improvements in some metrics, $b = 4$ offered a better balance between performance, as reflected in BERTScore, and computational efficiency. Moreover, as shown in Table 5.2, LLaVA-1.5 consistently outperforms InstructBLIP across all metrics on the development (private test) set, producing more accurate captions (Section 5.2.2). Finally, Table 5.5 illustrates that compared to the DMMCS [Kal+24] decoding procedure (Section 5.2.2), LLaVA-1.5 exhibits a decline in performance.

Tab. 5.4: Beam Search and Performance Scores for Fine-Tuned LLaVA-1.5 on the Validation Set.

LLaVA-1.5 - Results					
Prompt	Beams	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
1	1	56,30	13,85	26,86	14,2
	4	57,92	14,85	28,60	17,1
	5	57,60	15,53	30,85	16,6
2	1	57,56	15,82	30,75	14,8
	4	59,62	18,55	31,40	18,8
	5	59,40	20,52	30,70	19,1
3	1	58,81	19,92	28,68	17,3
	4	61,58	22,03	30,49	20,4
	5	60,52	21,64	30,74	21,1

Tab. 5.5: Performance Scores for LLaVA-1.5 compared with and without DMMCS.

LLaVA-1.5 with and without DMMCS - Results				
Model	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
SFT LLaVA-1.5	62,08	22,53	30,99	20,6
LLaVA-1.5 with DMMCS	61,90	21,80	29,12	20,8

¹<https://huggingface.co/llava-hf/llava-1.5-7b-hf>, Last accessed: 2024-11-30

5.2.4 LLaVA 1.5 with Few Shot Examples

Extensive research has focused on how LLMs and MLLMs comprehend instructions [Bro+20; Ala+24]. These models can be *prompted* to perform various tasks by providing them with examples of the task as input. A common approach is to provide the model with examples consisting of image-caption pairs to assess its ability to generate similar captions [CLF24]. ICL is advocated as an alternative to fine-tuning, especially when limited data is available. Unlike supervised training, ICL is a training-free approach that significantly reduces computational costs in adapting models to tasks. The core idea is that the model learns by analogy, integrating a few-shot examples with the prompt before feeding them into an LLM. This technique avoids modifying the model parameters, instead focusing on enabling the model to discern hidden patterns in the examples to generate accurate predictions [Don+24]. A widely adopted method [Wan+19; Liu+21; Aga+24; PL22] involves extracting the k -nearest neighbors from the training data and incorporating them into the prompt. Figure 5.2 presents an example of a chest X-ray image, along with the prompt used and the image-caption pairs that serve as few-shot examples for this case.

Table 5.7 demonstrates a comparison between a gold caption, randomly selected from the development (private test) set (Section 4), and captions generated by InstructBLIP, InstructBLIP with DMMCS, and LLaVA-1.5, utilizing both fine-tuning and few-shot examples for the same image. The results show that the fine-tuned LLaVA-1.5 caption is closer to the gold caption, as indicated by the BERTScore (Section 5.1.3), but it is still far from perfect and does not fully match the accuracy and coherence of the gold caption.

Tab. 5.6: Performance Scores for LLaVA-1.5 compared with and without few shot examples.

LLaVA-1.5 with and without Few Shot Examples - Results				
Model	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
Few Shot LLaVA-1.5	59,02	20,60	28,25	17,6
SFT LLaVA-1.5	62,08	22,53	30,99	20,6

However, this method has proven less effective due to inconsistency in the gold captions. Section 4.1.2 outlines that the dataset provided [Rüc+24a] displays some surprising trends, where captions can vary dramatically from 1 word to as many as 848 words, a pattern also illustrated in Figure 4.3(a). This shows significant diversity among captions and a lack of a specific template, which is an important feature for a dataset [PKA19]. Some captions are clear and concise, accurately describing the image, while others provide only basic information, such as the image modality, or include irrelevant details unrelated to the actual content, as illustrated through several examples in Table 5.8. As a result, the few-shot technique, which aims to uncover hidden patterns to generate new captions, did not improve the model evaluation metrics. Table 5.9 shows that the BertScore (Section 5.1.3) decreased when few shot examples were used.

Fig. 5.2: Prompt and sample image-caption pairs illustrate the expected relationship between the visuals and their corresponding descriptions, helping the model learn how to generate appropriate captions. The image displays three pairs of image-caption examples, which serve as few-shot examples for the model. The fourth image acts as the test case, where the model is required to generate a diagnostic caption by following the patterns established in the prior examples. These pairs are sourced from [Rüc+24a].

5.2.5 Llama 3.1 Synthesizer

In the Synthesizer method outlined in Section 3.3, the core idea is to improve the generated caption by leveraging images similar to the one being tested. Similar images are defined as those that share common characteristics, such as the medical modality or the organ depicted. The key difference between the Synthesizer method and the few-shot techniques discussed in Section 5.2.4 is that the Synthesizer aims to uncover valuable information from neighboring images, while few-shot focuses on prompting the model to mimic the demonstrations and identify patterns.

To determine whether two images are neighbors, image embeddings must be extracted using a CNN-FFNN framework [Cha+21; Cha+22; Kal+23]. In this setup, a CNN encoder acts as the backbone, followed by an FFNN classification head as shown in Figure 3.5. Image features are extracted from the final convolutional layer of the encoder and merged

Tab. 5.7: Comparison of the gold caption and the generated captions for the same image. The red highlights indicate shared components between the captions, such as common anatomical structures, imaging modalities, or clinical details.

Model	Caption	BertScore
Gold Caption	A 6-year-old female patient presenting to ED with suprapubic pain. Sagittal view US image shows a round-shaped cystic lesion (arrows) above the superior surface of the bladder (star). Due to the mixed echogenicity of the lesion, it was considered an infected urachal cyst . Surgical findings confirmed the diagnosis.	-
InstructBLIP	The image displays a black and white ultrasound of a pregnant woman's uterus. The uterus is filled with amniotic fluid, indicating a healthy pregnancy.	59,99
InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS	Ultrasound of the abdomen showing a dilated aorta.	61,08
LLaVA 1.5 Few Shots	Ultrasound of a 18-year-old female with fat-fluid level in a mature cystic lesion .	64,18
SFT LLaVA 1.5	A 50-year-old man with a hepatic hemangioma in the right lobe. Sagittal US shows a well-defined, hypoechoic mass (arrows) .	69.49

into a feature vector using the Generalized-Mean (GeM) pooling mechanism [RTC19]. The images, resized to 224×224 pixels, are processed using the CNN encoder, and embeddings are extracted from the final convolutional layer. These images belong to the private training and validation sets (Section 4). Once the embeddings are extracted, the same procedure is conducted on the development (private test) set. Subsequently, the k -NN algorithm is employed to retrieve images from the training set that meet a specified cosine similarity threshold [Lew+20; Gao+24].

As described in Section 3.3, LLaMA-3.1 Instruct [Gra+24] with 8 billion parameters² serves as the Synthesizer model. This MLLM is pre-trained using IT (Section 2.3), so its performance is closely tied to the quality of prompts provided. The input to the model includes the test image, a draft caption generated by InstructBLIP (Section 3.1) or LLaVA-1.5 (Section 3.2.1), along with the number of neighbors determined by various thresholds. Figure 5.3 shows a prompt that covers both scenarios: when neighboring captions are available and when they are not. In the case where neighbors are present, the model is instructed to incorporate relevant information from them to enhance the generated caption. If no neighboring captions are available, the model generates the caption solely based on the information in the test image.

The first step involved setting a threshold to determine which images would be considered neighbors, along with identifying the optimal number of neighbors needed to generate

²<https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct>, Last accessed: 2024-11-30

Tab. 5.8: Captions vary in the amount of information they provide, with some being less informative and others containing more information than necessary.

Medical Imaging Captions	
No.	Caption
1	Proctography.
2	Radiography of the chest.
3	Sagittal view of CT thorax.
4	Radiograph of a bony skier’s thumb.
5	Chest x-ray, anatomic deviation after left pneumonectomy.
6	Anteroposterior chest X-ray. The right internal jugular cannula is visible. Arrow, catheter tip. Suture of the catheter tip to the heart was highly suspected, and another thoracotomy was scheduled on postoperative day eight. Movement was noted at the interatrial groove incision near the atrial-caval junction while extracting the catheter. Four needles were made with mattress suture around the interatrial groove incision, and the catheter was removed easily after loosening the original threads, which suggested that the catheter had been sutured to the atrial septal tissue. Our patient had an uneventful recovery and the endotracheal tube was extracted the next day.
7	Magnetic resonance images of a true epidural lipomatosis. A T1-weighted cross-sectional image of a true epidural lipomatosis at the lumbar level of L4/L5 (according to Borré). There is a large intraspinal space, which is filled by an excessive amount of epidural fat (white arrows) and squeezes the cerebrospinal fluid away so that the dural sac (black arrow) completely surrounds the bundle of nerve roots and leaving no free intradural cerebrospinal fluid volume (dural sac cross-sectional area of only 48 mm ²). These nerve roots are not completely free to move away when a needle is inserted into the dural sac.

Tab. 5.9: Performance Scores for LLaVA-1.5 compared with and without Few-Shot Examples

LLaVA-1.5 with and without Few-Shot Examples				
	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
LLaVA-1.5 SFT	62,08	22,53	30,99	20,8
LLaVA-1.5 with Few-Shot Examples	59,02	20,60	28,25	17,6

the most accurate final caption. As shown in Figure 5.4, increasing the thresholds results in fewer neighbors that are more similar to each other, while decreasing the thresholds yields a wider selection of neighbors, although the similarity percentage is lower. This introduces a trade-off, highlighting the need to determine the ideal number of neighbors that enhances the caption without adding unnecessary verbosity.

Tables 5.10 present a comparison of the BERTScore [Dev+19] and ROUGE-L [Lin04] metrics for captions created by LLaVA-1.5 [Liu+24b] and InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS [KP23] on the validation set (Section 4). For LLaVA-1.5, the highest BERTScore of 63,55 is achieved with a cosine similarity threshold of 0,90 when using a single neighbor. This suggests that utilizing a single similar caption provides the most relevant context without introducing

SYSTEM
 You are an experienced medical professional assistant.

USER
 In one concise sentence (up to 50 words), describe the content of the medical image by specifying the imaging modality (e.g., X-ray, CT, ultrasonography, MRI), the organ or body part involved, and any significant findings or abnormalities. If available, incorporate relevant details from the neighboring caption to refine and enhance the draft caption. Do not include information not present in the image or caption. If there is no neighboring caption, refine the caption using only the information from the image.

Fig. 5.3: The prompt used for LLaMA-3.1 is designed to follow different instructions based on whether or not neighbors are present.

Fig. 5.4: Comparison of Average Number of Neighbors and Similarity with Threshold. As the cosine similarity threshold increases, the average similarity of neighbors (red color) rises, while the average number of neighbors (blue color) decreases significantly. Conversely, as the threshold decreases, the average similarity of neighbors fall, and the average number of neighbors increases.

unnecessary information. When more neighbors are included, the BERTScore tends to drop slightly, suggesting that these additional neighbors might introduce irrelevant details. For InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS, the best BERTScore is also reached at a cosine similarity threshold of 0,90 with a maximum score of 62,90 when using only a neighbor. This pattern is also seen in the ROUGE-L scores, indicating that the single neighbor chosen for LLaVA-1.5 contains information that is closer to the gold caption, but it is still quite far from fully matching it. It is crucial to emphasize that this analysis underscores the importance of not only the similarity threshold and the number of neighbors but also the quality of the initial captions. As demonstrated in Tables 5.2 and 5.4, LLaVA produced better captions. Consequently, the Synthesizer performs better in terms of metrics when using the initial captions generated by LLaVA-1.5.

Tab. 5.10: Comparison of BERTScore and ROUGE-L metrics for different initial captions generated by LLaVA-1.5 and InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS on the validation set, highlighting the impact of cosine similarity thresholds and the number of neighbors on the evaluation results.

Evaluation Metric: BERTScore				
	Similarity Threshold	1-neighbor	3-neighbors	5-neighbors
InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS	0.75	61,80	61,70	61,36
	0.80	62,00	61,18	60,80
	0.85	62,50	61,96	61,10
	0.90	62,90	61,75	61,50
	0.95	61,00	60,20	59,00
SFT LLaVA-1.5	0.75	62,20	62,08	60,48
	0.80	62,55	62,12	61,10
	0.85	63,00	62,35	61,50
	0.90	63,55	62,85	62,91
	0.95	60,39	59,10	58,84
Evaluation Metric: ROUGE-L				
	Similarity Threshold	1-neighbor	3-neighbors	5-neighbors
InstructBLIP ft. DMMCS	0.75	20,15	19,50	18,30
	0.80	21,00	20,10	19,00
	0.85	20,85	19,80	18,50
	0.90	21,45	20,27	18,95
	0.95	20,80	19,15	18,10
SFT LLaVA-1.5	0.75	23,08	21,62	20,10
	0.80	22,80	22,37	21,80
	0.85	22,45	22,12	21,65
	0.90	23,29	22,58	21,63
	0.95	23,09	22,81	22,17

Table 5.11 provides a comparative analysis of all the models examined thus far, emphasizing the Synthesizer’s superior performance. Additionally, Table 5.12 demonstrates how the Llama synthesizer enhances the caption generated by LLaVA-1.5 [Liu+24b] by incorporating information from the neighboring image and the caption. Although LLaVA-1.5 successfully identifies the imaging modality as a CT scan, it fails to specify the body organ (pelvis). In contrast, the neighbor caption explicitly mentions the pelvis and accurately identifies the right side of the organ, aligning with the gold caption. The Llama 3, 1 Synthesizer uses this information to improve the draft caption, ensuring that both the modality and the organ are accurately described. However, it is important to note that, even after these improvements, the generated caption is still far from the gold caption in terms of accuracy and completeness.

Tab. 5.11: A comparison showing that the Synthesizer system is the most effective among the models discussed up to this section.

Performance Comparison Analysis				
	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
SFT Instructblip	61,64	19,31	27,85	10,0
InstructBLIP w DMMCS	62,11	20,49	28,99	11,1
SFT LLaVA-1.5	62,08	22,53	30,99	20,8
LLaVA-1.5 with Few-Shot Examples	59,02	20,60	28,25	17,6
LLaVA-1.5 with DMMCS	61,90	21,80	29,12	20,8
Llama 3.1 Synthesizer	63,55	23,29	32,44	21,7

Tab. 5.12: Example of how the Synthesizer enhances the draft caption in comparison to the gold caption. The captions for both the Gold and Neighbor are sourced from [Rüc+24a].

Model	Caption	BertScore
Gold Caption	Stir axial CT of the pelvis showing oedema within the soft tissue involving the right piriformis muscle, extending into the gluteal muscles on the right side.	-
Neighbor Caption	MDCT Helical axial cut of the pelvis showing the prostate is enlarged with a faint ring-enhancing lesion measuring 3×2.7×3 cm (white arrow). Note: The lesion takes up most of the right side of the prostate, extending to the right seminal vesicles. Abbreviation: MDCT, multiple detector computed tomography.	-
SFT LLaVA-1.5	Computed tomography scan showing rectal wall thickening and perirectal fat stranding. There is no evidence of rectal mass or lymphadenopathy. Bowel loops are in the presacral space.	62,27
Llama Synthesizer	A CT scan of the pelvis reveals an enlarged prostate with a 3x2.7x3 cm ring-enhancing lesion occupying most of the right side, extending to the right seminal vesicles.	70.79

5.2.6 LM-Fuser

Fine-tuning is resource-intensive, few-shot learning is cost-effective but less efficient, and relying heavily on the characteristics of neighboring captions may lead to the selection of irrelevant ones. By avoiding these issues, this approach presents a more resource-efficient strategy while still yielding effective results. Rather than modifying model weights, it leverages the knowledge captured by various MLLMs during inference. A more efficient LM is fine-tuned to integrate this information by using the outputs from the MLLMs, offering a more cost-effective solution. This method is effective because this model can access multiple candidate outputs for the same sequence, as illustrated in Figure 3.10.

The initial step was to select the models responsible for generating candidate captions for the training and validation sets (Section 4). The selected models were the same as those described in Section 3, specifically LLaVA-1.5 (Section 3.2.1) and LLaMA-3.1 (Section

3.3.2), with Idefics2 (Section 3.4.1) included as well. This selection was made to ensure a more justified comparison between all the methods tested, utilizing the models with their initial weights and without fine-tuning on a specific dataset. The resulting training and validation sets consisted of images, their corresponding gold captions, and three alternative captions generated by the selected models. The LM-Fuser was fine-tuned using the newly generated training dataset. Built on FLAN-T5 (Section 3.4.2), this model is specifically designed to integrate information solely from the outputs of the three candidate captions. Cross-entropy loss [ZS18] was used as the training loss function, while ROUGE-L [Lin04] was employed as the criterion for Early Stopping, chosen for its computational efficiency compared to BERTScore [Dev+19]. Hyperparameter optimization was performed to enhance the model’s performance. The learning rate started at 10^{-5} and was gradually decreased each epoch to reach the optimal value. This approach was adopted to benefit from an initially higher learning rate for rapid learning and significant weight updates, while the gradual reduction helped prevent overfitting or premature convergence to suboptimal solutions. The batch size was set to 4, balancing the benefits of frequent updates per epoch with the memory demands of smaller batches. The model was trained for 30 epochs, with Early Stopping implemented, allowing a patience of 3 epochs.

In the generation process, LM-Fuser initially utilizes captions produced by the MLLMs and subsequently produces the final captions by first concatenating the logits from multiple candidate captions. Logits are the raw outputs from the model’s final layer, indicating the probability of each vocabulary word in the vocabulary being the next word in the caption. A softmax function is then applied to convert these logits into a probability distribution over the vocabulary. Using beam search with a beam size of $b = 4$, the next word in the caption is selected by considering the top 4 most likely sequences at each step. This process continues iteratively until a complete caption is formed, typically ending with a special token that marks the end of the caption. This approach ensures that the generated caption is contextually appropriate, utilizing information from multiple sources. As discussed in Section 3.4.2, FLAN-T5 [Chu+24] can be customized to follow specific instructions. Figure 5.5 presents the evaluation metrics over 5 epochs, with a focus on the specific epoch when Early Stopping was applied. In the figure, the evaluation loss for *Instruction 1* is represented by the blue curve, while the orange dashed curve corresponds to *Instruction 2*. Notably, the orange dashed curve shows a lower loss than the blue curve, indicating better performance for *Instruction 2*.

Table 5.13 provides an evaluation of several prompts to identify the most efficient one. Additionally, Table 5.14 compares the evaluation metrics for captions produced by the top-performing prompts during both the training and inference stages of the model. These experiments were performed in the development (private test) set (Section 4).

Table 5.15 compares the original gold caption with three alternative captions generated by LLaVA 1.5 (Section 3.2.1), LLaMA 3.1 (Section 3.3.2), and Idefics2 (Section 3.4.1). It

Fig. 5.5: Evaluation of the LM-Fuser model using ROUGE-L, trained for 10 epochs with EarlyStopping at epoch 5. The figure displays the evaluation loss at epoch 5.

Tab. 5.13: Instruction Prompts for LM-Fuser Model.

Instruction Prompts for LM-Fuser Model	
ID	Instruction
1	"Given the following three descriptions, generate a single, detailed, and coherent caption that captures the essence of all three while being more concise."
2	"As a medical expert, generate a clear and concise caption for the medical image that synthesizes the following three descriptions. Your caption should seamlessly weave together the key points from all three descriptions, maintaining a clear, unified narrative that avoids repetition while highlighting their unique contributions."

also includes the caption produced by the LM-Fuser model. While all captions reference ultrasound images, the LM-Fuser-generated caption achieves the highest BERTScore

Tab. 5.14: Instruction Prompts and Performance Scores for LM-Fuser Model.

Instruction Prompts for LM-Fuser Model		Performance Metrics			
ID	Instruction	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
1	"Given the following three descriptions, generate a single, detailed, and coherent caption that captures the essence of all three while being more concise."	64,18	23,54	30,46	19,7
2	"As a medical expert, generate a clear and concise caption for the medical image that synthesizes the following three descriptions. Your caption should seamlessly weave together the key points from all three descriptions, maintaining a clear, unified narrative that avoids repetition while highlighting their unique contributions."	65,27	24,40	31,99	21,4

[Zha+19]. Finally, Table 5.16 provides an overview of all the methods implemented in this thesis, emphasizing LM-Fuser as the model with the best metrics.

Tab. 5.15: Comparison of the gold caption with the three candidate captions and the caption generated by LM-Fuser. As LM-Fuser achieves the highest BERTScore, it generates the most descriptive caption. Gold caption taken from [Rüc+24a].

Model	Captions	BERTScore
Gold Caption	A 6-year-old female patient presenting to the ED with suprapubic pain. Sagittal view US image shows a round-shaped cystic lesion (arrows) above the superior surface of the bladder (star). Due to the mixed echogenicity of the lesion, it was considered an infected urachal cyst. Surgical findings confirmed the diagnosis.	-
LLaVA-1.5	us with a hepatic hemangioma in the right lobe.	48,84
LLaMA-3.1	The ultrasound-guided needle biopsy image shows a well-positioned needle within the hepatic hemangioma , with a white arrow pointing to adjacent pleural thickening.	49,66
Idefics2	Ultrasound image of the abdomen shows a 17-week pregnant woman with a unilocular cystic lesion in the right ovary measuring 6.5 x 5.5 cm.	54,02
LM-Fuser	Sagittal US shows a well-defined hypochoic mass (arrows) in the right lobe of the liver .	55,37

Tab. 5.16: Summary of the methods implemented in this thesis, with LM-Fuser achieving the best metrics.

Performance Comparison Analysis				
	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEURT	BLEU
SFT Instructblip	61,64	19,31	27,85	10,0
InstructBLIP w DMMCS	62,11	20,49	28,99	11,1
SFT LLaVA-1.5	62,08	22,53	30,99	20,8
LLaVA-1.5 with Few-Shot Examples	59,02	20,60	28,25	17,6
LLaVA-1.5 with DMMCS	61,90	21,80	29,12	20,8
Llama 3.1 Synthesizer	63,55	23,29	32,44	21,7
LM-Fuser	64,27	24,40	31,99	20,4

5.2.7 ImageCLEFmedical Caption 2024 Submissions

A significant part of this thesis was carried out as part of the participation of the AUEB NLP Group in the 2024 ImageCLEFmedical competition [Ion+24]. Our team secured 2nd place in the Concept Detection task and 4th place in the Caption Prediction task [Sam+24]. For the Caption Prediction task, we started by generating captions using the InstructBLIP model [Dai+24]. We then enhanced these captions by integrating information from similar image captions [Gao+24; Ver+24], based on the work of the AUEB NLP Group, with similarity being the cosine similarity of embeddings derived from a CNN-FFNN model [Kal+23; Cha+22; Cha+21]. FLAN-T5 [Chu+24] was used as the Synthesizer Model (Section 3.3). Additionally, we submitted a system that combined InstructBLIP with DMMCS [Kal+24]. Since DMMCS depends on the hyperparameter α , we tested various values to identify its optimal setting. Ultimately, the winning model incorporated InstructBLIP as the primary caption generator for the draft diagnostic report, using DMMCS with $\alpha = 0,1$.

Table 5.17 presents the performance scores and rankings of the submitted systems for the Caption Prediction sub-task, summarizing the results across all officially reported metrics. These metrics include BERTScore [Zha+19], ROUGE-L [Lin04], BLEU-1 [Pap+02], BLEURT [SDP20], METEOR [BL05], CIDEr [VZP15], CLIPscore [Hes+22], RefCLIPscore [Hes+22], ClinicalBLEURT [SDP20], and MedBERTScore [Aba+23]. METEOR evaluates the quality of generated captions by combining precision, recall, synonym matching, and stemming. CIDEr is specifically designed for image captioning, focusing on the agreement between multiple reference captions and the generated caption, with particular attention to rare terms. CLIPscore assesses the relevance of captions by comparing the alignment between the generated caption and image features from the CLIP model. RefCLIPscore operates similarly to CLIPscore but evaluates the alignment between the generated caption and reference caption embeddings. ClinicalBLEURT, a variant of BLEURT, is tailored for medical texts and measures the similarity between medical captions and their references.

MedBERTScore, based on BERT, is adapted to assess the quality of captions in the medical domain. The evaluations were conducted using the official evaluation dataset of the competition [Rüc+24b], which differs from the held-out development (private test set) used throughout this thesis. Table 5.18 illustrates the correspondence between the submission IDs and the submitted models.

Tab. 5.17: Summary of our submissions for the Caption Prediction sub-task. The table presents the performance of each system across all officially reported metrics.

AUEB NLP Group Submissions - Evaluation on All Metrics											
ID	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	BLEU-1	BLEURT	METEOR	CIDEr	CLIPscore	RefCLIPscore	ClinicalBLEURT	MedBERTScore	Rank
630	0.6211	0.2049	0.1110	0.2899	0.0680	0.1769	0.8041	0.7987	0.4866	0.6261	10
635	0.6210	0.2047	0.1108	0.2895	0.0680	0.1762	0.8040	0.7986	0.4870	0.6260	11
646	0.6210	0.2044	0.1107	0.2900	0.0678	0.1758	0.8041	0.7988	0.4872	0.6261	12
647	0.6210	0.1807	0.0860	0.2846	0.0580	0.1459	0.7936	0.7912	0.5021	0.6291	13
650	0.6160	0.1936	0.1050	0.2859	0.0638	0.1597	0.7980	0.7948	0.4874	0.6212	20
564	0.6153	0.2052	0.1274	0.2920	0.0698	0.1769	0.8045	0.7968	0.4844	0.6197	22
605	0.6114	0.1889	0.1147	0.2796	0.0616	0.1305	0.8037	0.7962	0.4834	0.6174	24
639	0.6111	0.1827	0.0744	0.2717	0.0515	0.1293	0.7858	0.7845	0.5212	0.6141	25
577	0.6107	0.1838	0.0751	0.2706	0.0513	0.1292	0.7832	0.7826	0.5158	0.6134	26

Tab. 5.18: Mapping of Run ID to System for the ImageCLEFmedical2024 Caption Prediction sub-task.

ImageCLEFmedical Caption 2024 - Submission IDs	
ID	System
564	InstructBLIP
577	InstructBLIP + Rephraser
605	InstructBLIP + Synthesizer
630	InstructBLIP + DMMCS ($\alpha = 0.1$)
635	InstructBLIP + DMMCS ($\alpha = 0.05$)
639	InstructBLIP + Synthesizer + Rephraser
647	InstructBLIP + DMMCS ($\alpha = 0.1$) + ClinicalT5
650	InstructBLIP + DMMCS ($\alpha = 0.1$) + ClinicalT5 (random restart)
646	InstructBLIP + DMMCS ($\alpha = 0.15$)

Conclusions & Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This thesis explored the domain of biomedical image captioning, commonly known as Diagnostic Captioning (DC). This task involves generating text to provide draft medical interpretations of radiology images, helping healthcare professionals. DC systems are intended to support the diagnostic process, aiding healthcare practitioners who frequently deal with time pressures and heavy patient caseloads, while complementing their expertise rather than replacing it. [PKA19; Pav+22].

Multi-modal Large Language Models (MLLMs) [CFS24; Yin+24; Wu+23] were analyzed, focusing on strategies for their fine-tuning using quantization methods in hardware-constrained scenarios, while also investigating the application of few-shot techniques. To improve the accuracy and relevance of the generated captions, information is synthesized from retrieved similar images [Lew+20; Gao+24], grounded in the idea that similar images typically have similar captions. Similar images are defined as those sharing common features, such as the same image modality (X-ray, Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), or Ultrasound) or depicting the same organ. Additionally, to mitigate the high cost of using MLLMs, this research explores training a more efficient language model (LM) that leverages the alternative outputs of MLLMs [Ver+24; JRL23]. Inspired by the fact that clinicians frequently consult with colleagues to gain a comprehensive understanding of a patient's medical condition, multiple MLLMs generate captions for the training and validation sets without fine-tuning on a specific dataset, relying on their initial weights and the same prompt. Subsequently, a smaller model is trained using these captions, aiming to produce a more concise caption by merging multiple captions for a single image.

In conclusion, this work highlights advancements in NLP and the growing potential of MLLMs to significantly enhance DC systems. This study used state-of-the-art (SOTA) MLLMs with fine-tuning and few-shot learning [Liu+22], alongside retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) techniques [Lew+20] and an ensembling method to integrate information from multiple MLLMs [Ver+24]. Furthermore, this research contributed to the AUEB NLP Group's participation in the ImageCLEFmed2024 competition [Ion+24], with the author as a primary contributor [Sam+24]. The group achieved 2nd place in Concept Detection and 4th in Caption Prediction, competing against 9 and 11 teams, respectively.

6.2 Future Work

A promising direction for future research in DC involves a more in-depth exploration of MLLMs, particularly focusing on caption generation. Although these models offer significant potential in the biomedical domain [YLW23; Als+19; NP24; Tu+24], it is essential to recognize their limitations. An important limitation involves hallucinations [Ji+23], characterized by scenarios where the model produces outputs that are either factually incorrect or not corroborated by the given data. Since these models are often regarded as black boxes, it is vital for researchers to understand how outputs are generated, particularly in the biomedical field, where the decisions made and the processes that inform them are crucial [Thi+23]. By intervening in the decoding process, researchers can assess and potentially rank possible outputs [JRL23] based on specific instructions. Furthermore, given LM-Fuser's (Section 3.4.3) strong performance in this thesis, alternative fusion techniques should be investigated, such as weight averaging, to optimize the influence of candidates on the final caption.

Another important area for research involves creating a communication channel with clinicians to enhance the evaluation processes of MLLMs [Tan+24]. Current evaluation metrics are often inadequate, especially in the biomedical field. Engaging medical experts in the evaluation procedure could help better fine-tune metrics, such as BLEURT [SDP20], to enhance their relevance and provide more meaningful medical insights. This collaboration paves the way for fine-tuning methods that align language models using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF). This technique utilizes human preferences as rewards to refine the models, enabling MLLMs to adjust their outputs based on continuous feedback from healthcare professionals [Ouy+22]. Moreover, collaborating with healthcare professionals to create a dataset that meets specified criteria could enhance the evaluation process by ensuring alignment with clinical outcomes [Pav+22]. For instance, establishing a template for the captions that must be adhered to, along with defining maximum and minimum lengths, would foster consistency and clarity throughout the dataset. Researchers often lack medical expertise and depend on evaluation metrics that may not accurately reflect the challenges faced by medical professionals.

In conclusion, another important area that warrants investigation is the use of more effective prompts, as they are crucial for enhancing the performance of MLLMs. These models are trained to follow instructions and generally achieve higher accuracy when given well-structured prompts [Wan+24; Rus+24], emphasizing the importance of refining the crafting of these prompts. Medical professionals can play a vital role in this process by sharing their expertise in chain of thought reasoning techniques [Wei+24] and providing few-shot examples [Don+24; Liu+22; CLF24], ensuring that model outputs meet their expectations.

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List of Acronyms

BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BLEU	BiLingual Evaluation Understudy
BLEURT	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy with Representations from Transformers
BP	Brevity Penalty
CC3M	Conceptual Captions 3M
CNNs	Convolutional Neural Networks
CT	Computed Tomography
CUI	Concept Unique Identifiers
DMMCS	Distance from Median Maximum Concept Similarity
DC	Diagnostic Captioning
DL	Deep Learning
FFNN	Feed-Forward Neural Network
FLAN-T5	Fine-tuned LAnguage Net T5
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
HMMs	Hidden Markov Models
ICL	In-Context Learning

IT	Instruction Tuning
kNN	k -Nearest Neighbours
LCS	Longest Common Subsequence
LLaVA	Large Language and Vision Assistant
Llama	Large Language Model Meta AI
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LM	Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
MLLMs	Multimodal Large Language Models
MLM	Masked Language Modeling
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MIC	Medical Image Captioning
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NL	Natural Language
NLG	Natural Language Generation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NSP	Next Sentence Prediction
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OOV	Out-Of-Vocabulary
PEFT	Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning
Q-Former	Querying Transformer

RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
RNNs	Recurrent Neural Networks
ROCO	Radiology Objects in COntext
ROCOv2	Radiology Objects in COntext Version 2
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
SFT	Supervised Fine-Tuning
SOTA	State-Of-The-Art
TL	Transfer Learning
T5	Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
VLMs	Vision Language Models
VQA	Visual Question Answering
ViTs	Vision Transformers

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